

THE NEW DATA ON CALLIPHORIDAE AND RHINOPHORIDAE (DIPTERA) FROM UKRAINE

Yu.G.Verves

Department of Entomology, Institute of Plant Protection
Vasykivska St. 33, Kyiv, 03022, Ukraine

E-mail: fly_@voliacable.com

L.A.Khrokalo

Department of Environmental Biotechnology and Bioenergy
National Technical University of Ukraine
Peremogy Ave., 37, Kyiv, 03056, Ukraine

E-mail: lkhrokalo@mail.com

Verves Yu.G. & Khrokalo L.A. The new data on Calliphoridae and Rhinophoridae (Diptera) from Ukraine. Summary. — The faunistic data of the results of collecting calliphorids (49 species) and rhinophorids (7 species) in different regions of Ukraine during 2005–2009 in general are presented. From 69 species of Calliphoridae two (*Bellardia vespillo* and *Lucilia cuprina*) are firstly recorded for Ukraine, of them 20 for Sumy, 19 for Poltava, 7 for Kyiv City, 6 for Odesa, 4 for Mykolayiv, 3 for Krym Republic (Crimea), Ivano-Frankivsk, Kherson, Zhytomyr, 2 for Kyiv, Lugansk, Lviv, a single species for Cherkasy, Kirovograd, Rivne, Ternopil, Volyn, Zakarpattya and Zaporizhzhya Regions. From 15 known species of Rhinophoridae two ones are firstly recorded for Lugansk, Odesa, Poltava, Sumy, and a single species for Kherson, Zaporizhzhya and Zhytomyr regions. The literature and original data on station distribution, food and others ecological aspects of the species are also presented.

Key words: Diptera, Calliphoridae, Rhinophoridae, fauna, Ukraine.

Вервес Ю.Г., Хрокало Л.А. Новые данные о Calliphoridae и Rhinophoridae (Diptera) из Украины. Резюме. — Представлены результаты фаунистических сборов каллифорид (49 видов) и ринофорид (7 видов) в различных областях Украины преимущественно за 2005–2009 гг. Из 69 найденных в Украине видов Calliphoridae два (*Bellardia vespillo* и *Lucilia cuprina*) впервые указаны для ее территории, 20 — для Сумской обл., 19 — для Полтавской, 7 — для г. Киева, 6 — для Одесской, 4 — для Николаевской, по 3 — для Житомирской, Ивано-Франковской, Республики Крым, Херсонской, по 2 — для Киевской, Луганской, Львовской, по одному виду — для Волинской, Закарпатской, Запорожской, Кировоградской, Ровенской, Тернопольской и Черкасской областей. Из 15 известных для территории Украины видов Rhinophoridae по два вида впервые найдены в Луганской, Одесской, Полтавской Сумской, по одному — в Житомирской, Запорожской и Херсонской областях. Для каждого вида представлены литературные и оригинальные данные об его эколого-фаунистических особенностях.

Ключевые слова: Diptera, каллифориды, ринофориды, фауна, Украина.

Вервес Ю.Г., Хрокало Л.А. Нові дані про Calliphoridae та Rhinophoridae (Diptera) з України. Резюме. — Представлені результати фаунистичних зборів каліфорид (49 видів) та ринофорид (7 видів) в різних областях України переважно за 2005–2009 рр. Из 69 знайдених в Україні видів Calliphoridae два (*Bellardia vespillo* и *Lucilia cuprina*) вперше вказані для її території, 20 — для Сумської області, 19 — для Полтавської, 7 — для м. Києва, 6 — для Одеської, 4 — для Миколаївської, по 3 — для Житомирської, Івано-Франківської, Республіки Крим, Херсонської, по 2 — для Київської, Луганської, Львівської, по одному виду — для Волинської, Закарпатської, Запорізької, Кіровоградської, Рівненської, Тернопільської та Черкаської областей. Из 15 відомих для території України видів Rhinophoridae по два види вперше знайдені в Луганській, Одеській, Полтавській, Сумській областях, по одному — в Житомирській, Запорізькій та Херсонській областях. Для кожного виду наведені літературні та оригінальні дані про його еколого-фаунистичні особливості.

Ключові слова: Diptera, каліфориди, ринофориди, фауна, Україна.

Introduction

The faunistic data of the results of field collections of authors and some colleagues, and observations during several last years (2005–2009 in general) in different regions of Ukraine are presented.

The general distributional data are given after Artamonov (Артамонов, 1997), Baumgartner, Greenberg (1985), Bernotiene et al. (2006), Brothers (1999), Cais et al. (2001), Carvalho, Mello-Patiu (2008), Clemons (2001), Day (1948); Davies, Laurence (1992), Draber-Moňko (1989,

2004), Dumcĭius, Pakalniškis (2006), Emden (1954), Fan et al. (1997), González-Mora, Peris (1988), Grunin (1969; Грунин, 1966, 1970a, b, 1972, 1975), Gudjabidze (2000), Haenel et al. (1998), Hall (1948), Herting (1961, 1993), Herting, Tschorsnig (1998), Hicks (1959, 1962, 1971), James (1966, 1977), Kaczorowska (2006); Kano, Shinonaga (1968); Kurahashi (1967, 1987, 1993), Kurahashi, Chowanadisai (2001), Kurahashi, Kirk-Spriggs (2006), Kurahashi, Thapa (1994), Lehrer (1972), Lutovinovas (2004), Mariluis (1982), Mariluis, Mulieri (2003), Mariluis, Schnack (2002), Martínez-Sánchez et al. (1998), Mello

(2003), Ozerov (Озеров, 1986), Pape et al. (2001), Park (1977), Peris, González-Mora (1991), Peus (1960), Rognes (1987b, 1991, 1992a, b, 1997, 2002, 2003), Sabrosky et al. (1989), Schumann (1986), Sisojević et al. (1986), Skufyin, Khitsova (Скуфьин, Хицова, 1978), Stackelberg (Штакельберг, 1959, 1962), Sychevskaya (Сычевская, 1970, 1974), Thompson (1934), Verves (2001, 2003, 2004b-c, 2005d; Вєрвєс, 2004а), Vianna et al. (1998), Wallman (2001), Whitworth (2006), Wijnhoven, Zeegers (1999), Xue (2005), Zumpt (1956a, b) and some others. The genera of Calliphoridae are presented according Rognes (1991, 1998) and Verves, Khrokalo (Вєрвєс, Хрокало, 2006); Rhinophoridae - after Pape (1998). The first records are asterisked (*). The data on Ukrainian regions ("oblasts") and localities in each of regions and Kyiv City are given in alphabetical order.

Place of deposition of specimens is the private collection of the senior author.

Material and Methods

For collecting a hand net was used. Different localities of Kyiv City and its environs were observed during almost perennial 2005–2009 years. Inside of them more detailed investigations were provided by senior author during such expedition trips:

Krym Republic (Crimea): environs of Beregove village near Bakhchysarai, 44°54'20"N 33°37'E, dry meadows and loamy sea shore, 31.07–11.08.2004;

Kherson Region: Chornomorsky Nature Reserve, 46°20'N, 31°57'E, different branches; bushes and sandy areas, 18–29.07.2006;

Kyiv City (Centre: Angel Column, 50°27'70"N, 30°31'86"E), in different localities during all years;

Krym Republic (Crimea): Kazantip Nature Reserve, 45°28'N, 35°50'E, stones and dry steppe areas, 17–29.07.2007;

Zaporizzhya Region: environs of Altagir village, 46°37'33"N, 35°16'57"E, Biological station of Melitopol National Pedagogical University; sandy areas, meadows and bushes at banks of delta of Molochna River, 4–15.06.2008;

Poltava Region: environs of Pyryatyn, 50°15'N, 32°32'E, several localities; sandy areas, bogs, meadows, bushes, forests' borders etc. 8–18.07.2009;

Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, several localities; sandy areas, meadows and bushes at banks of Romenka River, 21–27.08.2009.

Annotated list of species

Calliphoridae

In Ukraine, the occurrence of 67 species of blowflies has been recorded so far (Khrokalo, Verves, 2009; Szpila, Verves, 2009; Verves, 2004c, 2005c). The Ukrainian fauna of Calliphoridae is relatively poorly studied. The state of knowledge of these dipterans is uneven for particular parts of Ukraine. Best known are the special lists of Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtsi, Kherson and Kyiv regions. Other regions are still with more or less scant data.

Bellardia bayeri (Jacentkovský, 1937)

Distribution. Holarctic: Europe northwards to Norway, including British Is. Asia: Russia (West Siberia, Southern Far East), Transcaucasia; North America: USA (Massachusetts, New Hampshire). Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernivtsi, Crimea, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv City*, Lviv, Lugansk, Poltava, Sumy* and Zakarpattya regions.

Material examined. Kyiv City: Berizka Lake, 50°26'17"N, 30°34'41"E, 20.09.2006, 1♂, 1♀; Chervonozoryany Prospekt, 50°24'23"N, 30°30'34"E, at trunks of trees, 27.09.2006, 43 males; Dubky Lake, 50°28'32"N, 30°25'43"E, 27.09.2006, 1♂; Vasylkivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 7.07–8.08.2008, 11♂, 2♀; *ibid.*, 18.05.2009, 1♀; *ibid.*, 30.09. — 5.10.2009, 17 males, 3 females (Yu. Verves). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 1♂ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. The viviparous females placed the larvae on coprolites of Lumbricidae according Veselkin (Веселкин, 1977); larvae are internal parasites of earthworms *Eisenia* sp. after Grunin (Грунин, 1970b) and *E. foetida* (Rognes, 1991). In Ukraine flies were collected from the end of April to the end of October with peaks in July and September. Flies prefer humid and mesophytic meadows, bushes, and forests. This is a culturophilous species: imagoes common in parks, gardens, yards with trees and bushes (Verves, 2005c).

Bellardia pandia (Walker, 1849)

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe northwards to Norway and Finland, including British Is.; Transcaucasia (Gruzia). Ukraine: Chernigiv, Chernivtsi, Khmelnytzkiy, Kyiv, Poltava, Sumy*, Volyn, Zakarpattya and Zaporizzhya regions.

Material examined. Poltava Region: Hrabarivka village, 50°22'52"N, 32°20'39"E, meadows nr Ruda River, 15.07.2009, 3♂, 4♀; *ibid.*, Shkuraty village, 50°12'41"N, 32°40'26"E, meadows, 17.07.2009, 1♀ (Yu. Verves). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 5♂, 2♀ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Flies feed on different flowers, and at leaves of *Ulmus* sp. at excreta of aphids *Pterocomma populeum* Kalt & *Tinocallis palatani* Kalt. In mountains flies were collected at altitudes to 1300 m a.s.l. (Draber-Moňko, 2004). Adult flies prefer different meadows, bushes, and forests;

not found in cultural landscapes; flying period in June–August, with peak in August (Verves, 2005c).

Bellardia polita (Mik, 1884)

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe northwards to Finland; absent on British Is. Ukraine: Crimea*, Cherkasy, Chernigiv and Sumy regions.

Material examined. Crimea: Kazantip Nature Reserve, 45°28'N, 35°50'E, 25.07.2007, 1♂ (Yu. Verves). Cherkasy Region: Moshny village, 49°32'00"N, 31°45'00"E, 19.06.1988, 1♀; Svydivok village, 49°30'46"N, 31°54'44"E, 17.06.1988, 1♀ (S. Zhrazhevsky); Lipyave village, 49°47'17"N, 31°04'00"E, board of lake, 26.06.1989, 1♀ (V. Kurasa).

Remarks. In Poland flying period is continued from May to September, flies feed on different flowering plants (Draber-Mońko, 2004).

Bellardia stricta (Villeneuve, 1926)

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe northwards to Norway, Finland, and Kola Peninsula, including British Is.; Asia: China (Heilongjiang), Russia (South Siberia & Primorye), Transcaucasia. Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtzi, Crimea, Khmelnyzky, Kyiv, Poltava*, Sumy*, Volyn, Zakarpattya and Zaporizhzhya regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Trakhtemyriv village, 49°57'20"N, 31°22'39"E, bank of stream, 13.07.1988, 1♂, 1♀ (S. Zhrazhevsky). Khmelnyzky Region: Stary Ostropol village, 49°48'40"N, 27°33'33"E, 21.05.1989, 1♀ (S. Zhrazhevsky). Kyiv City: Druzhby Narodiv Park, 50°30'16"N, 30°32'31"E, meadows nr Lake, 8.07.2005, 1♂; Vasylykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 7.07.2008, 1♀; *ibid.*, 18.05.2009, 1♀. Kyiv Region: Stugna River, 50°09'23"N, 30°44'01"E, at leaves and ground at border of pine forest nr Lake, 21.08.2004, 2♀; Tulyntsi village, 49°49'18"N, 31°10'49"E, bushes, 5.07.2007, 9♂, 3♀ (Yu. Verves). Poltava Region: Leliaky village, 50°19'41"N, 32°29'34"E, bank of Uday River, 15–17.07.2005, 1♀ (V. Gorobchyshyn); *ibid.*, Usivka village, 50°19'52"N, 32°31'47"E, meadows near Ruda River, 10 & 16.07.2009, 5♂, 14♀ (A. Drozdovska & Yu. Verves); *ibid.*, as prey of spider *Marpigga muscosa*, 16.07.2009, 1♀ (Singaevsky). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Sula River, 25.07.1989, 1♀ (S. Zhrazhevsky).

Remarks. Females are larviparous (Szpila, 2004). In Poland adult flies feed at excreta of aphids, flowers of *Cuscuta epithymum*; flying period is continued from May to September (Draber-Mońko, 2004). In Ukraine flies were collected in May–August with peak in the end of May–beginning of June. Flies prefer mesophytic meadows, bushes, and forests; very rare in cultural landscapes (Verves, 2005c).

Bellardia vespillo (Fabricius, 1894)

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe: Czech Republic, Denmark, Germany, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, The Netherlands. Ukraine: Kyiv Region*. Firstly recorded from Ukraine.

Material examined. Kyiv Region: Bila Tserkva, Park Oleksandriya, 49°48'47"N, 30°04'09"E, 3.05.2009, 1♂ (Yu. Verves).

Bellardia viarum (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe northwards to Norway, including British Is.; Asia: Japan (Honshu), Russia (West Siberia). Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernivtzi, Kyiv and Lugansk regions.

Material examined. Kyiv Region: Irpin, 50°31'11"N, 30°14'40"E, 1–15.07.1997, 1 male (V. Gorobchyshyn).

Remarks. In Poland flying period is continued from March to November, with peak in summer. Flies prefer different forests, meadows, cities. Imago feed at excreta of aphids *Anoesia corni* and *Eleucanium corni* and at different flowering plants (Draber-Mońko, 2004). In Ukraine several specimens were collected from the end of May to the end of October in synanthropic habitats and in hornbeam forest (Verves, 2005c).

Calliphora (s. str.) *loewi* Enderlein, 1903

Distribution. Holarctic: Europe northwards to Norway, incl. British Is.; Asia: China (Qinghai, Xinjian), Japan (Hokkaido, Honshu), Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, Mongolia, Russia (West Siberia: Altay; East Siberia: Yakutia; Far East: Amur Region, Primorye), Transcaucasia; North America: Canada (British Columbia, Newfoundland, Yukon Territory), USA (Alaska). Oriental Region: China (Yunnan), India (Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Uttaranchal), Nepal. Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtzi, Poltava*, Volyn and Zakarpattya* regions.

Material examined. Poltava Region: Hrabarivka village, 50°22'52"N, 32°20'39"E, meadows nr Ruda River, 15.07.2009, 1♂ (A. Drozdovska, V. Gorobchyshyn, Yu. Verves). Zakarpattya Region: Kolochava village, 48°26'12"N, 23°44'00"E, 500 m a. beech forest near Biological station, 14.08.1995, 2♂, 1♀ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Larvae bred in corpses of vertebrate animals and faeces (Pape et al., 2001). Imago prefers forested areas and uplands, particularly heather moor (Davies, Laurence, 1992; Nuorteva, 1963, 1966), in mountains to altitude about 3700 m, at alpine flowers (Kurahashi, Thapa, 1994). In Poland this species is not synanthropic. Flies attracted to *Phallus impudicus*, faeces, feed at flowers of Asteraceae and Apiaceae. Flying period from May to September, with peak in August, the most quantity of imagoes is in pine and others types of forests, rare at meadows (Draber-Mońko, 2004).

Calliphora (s. str.) *uralensis* Villeneuve, 1922

Distribution. Holarctic: Europe northwards to Norway, including British Is. and Iceland; Asia: China (Gansu, Hebei, Neimenggu, Qinghai, Sichuan, Xinjiang), Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, Mongolia, Russia (Siberia, Far East), Tibet, Transcaucasia; North Africa: Tunisia. North America: Greenland. Oriental Region: Pakistan (Northern Areas, North-West Frontier Province). Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernivtzi, Crimea, Donetsk, Kharkiv, Kherson, Kyiv, Odesa, Sumy*, Vinnytzya, Volyn, Zakarpattya and Zaporizhzhya regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Uman, Park Sophiivka, 48°44'29"N, 30°13'43"E, 13–14.06.2006, 1♂ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv City: Golosievsky Lakes, 50°22'30"N, 30°30'30"E, humid meadows, 12.09.2005, 1♂; Kozacha street, 50°24'01"N, 30°30'05"E, on leaves &

walls, 7.07.2005, 1♂; Malynivka Lake, 50°29'11"N, 30°34'18"E, bushes on bank, 23.06.2005, 1♂; Sonyachne Lake, 50°38'22"N, 30°38'23"E, 4.10.2006, 1♀; Vasylykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 5.07.2008, 1♀; *ibid.*, 26.11.2009, 5♀ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv Region: Irpin, 50°31'11"N, 30°14'40"E, 1–15.07.1997, 1♂ (V. Gorobchyshyn). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 2♂, 3♀ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Synanthropic species. Larvae develop in corpses of vertebrate animals and faeces. Adults are known as the vectors of diseases: *Salmonella*, cholera, dysentery, after Grunin, 1970a, 1972 (Грунин, 1970a, 1972); Stackelberg, 1959 (Штакельберг, 1959). Larvae produce facultative cutaneous myiasis in Eurasian elk, *Alces alces* (Akhmetov, Baidavletov, 2000). In Ukraine flies were collected from the beginning of March to the beginning of November at meadows, in bushes, secondary forests and synanthropic localities (Verves, 2005c).

Calliphora (s. str.) *vicina* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Distribution. All parts of Holarctic and Oriental regions, Australia and Pacific Is., South Africa, Mauritius I., Central and South Americas, Antarctic (Kerguelen I. and South Georgia Is.). Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtzi, Crimea, Donetsk, Kharkiv, Khmelnyzky, Kyiv, Kherson, Lugansk, Lviv, Mykolaiv, Odesa, Poltava, Sumy*, Ternopil, Vinnytyza, Volyn, Zakarpattya, Zaporizhzhya and Zhytomyr regions.

Material examined. Crimea: Beregove village, 44°54'20"N 33°37'E, sandy area, 10.08.2004, 1♀; Grand Canyon, 44°31'40"N, 34°01'00"E, 18.08.2001, 1♀ (Yu. Verves); Kazantip Nature Reserve, 45°28'N, 35°50'E, 10–13.05.2005, 2♀ (L. Khrokallo). Kherson Region: Chornomorsky Nature Reserve, 46°20'N, 31°57'E, Rybalchasnysky branch, near living buildings, 24.07.2006, 1♂, 1♀; *ibid.*, Solenoozerny branch, bank of see, 28.07.2006, 3♂ (Yu. Verves); Novo-Oleksiyivka village, near pig farm, at horse dung, 4.09.1961, 2♂; *ibid.*, near poultry farm, at horse and pig dung, 5.09.1961, 1♀; *ibid.*, near pig farm, at pig dung, 6.09.1961, 1♂ (O. Viktorov-Nabokov). Kyiv City: Berizka Lake, 50°26'17"N, 30°34'41"E, banks, 20.09.2006, 2♀; Dubky Lake, 50°28'32"N, 30°25'43"E, 15.07.2005, 1♂, 1♀; *ibid.*, 27.09.2006, 1♂; Kozacha street, 50°24'01"N, 30°30'05"E, on leaves & walls, 7.07.2005, 1♂, *ibid.*, 22.06.2009, 1♂; *ibid.*, 15.09.2009, 1♂; Kyiv-Pechersk Lavra, 50°26'06"N, 30°33'26"E, bushes at hills, 21.05.2009, 9♂, 14♀; Lopukhovate I., 50°30'22"N, 30°33'20"E, 26.09.2008, 2♀; Sonyachne Lake, 50°38'22"N, 30°38'23"E, 4.10.2006, 12♂, 11♀; Vasylykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 5–18.07.2008, 5♂, 7♀; *ibid.*, 18.05. — 26.11.2009, 64♂, 103♀ (Yu. Verves); Uralska street, 50°23'37"N, 30°31'30"E, 3–6.07.2009, 2♂ (A. Drozdovska). Kyiv Region: Bila Tserkva, Park Oleksandriya, 49°48'47"N, 30°04'09"E, 3.05.2009, 1♂ (Yu. Verves); Irpin, 50°31'11"N, 30°14'40"E, 1–15.07.1997, 4♂, 3♀ (V. Gorobchyshyn); Oseshchyna village, 50°34'33"N, 30°32'26"E, coast of lake, meadows, 3.06.2007, 1♀ (Yu. Verves). Poltava Region: Keybalivka village 50°18'34"N, 32°30'10"E, meadows, 18.07.2009, 2♂ (Yu. Verves); Mala Krucha village, 50°12'20"N, 32°33'26"E, 11–13.07.08, 1♂ (A. Drozdovska). Sumy Region: Vakalivschnyna village, 51°01'47"N, 34°55'12"E, humid meadow, 18–31.05.2006, 1♀ (O. Govorun). Zakarpattya Region: Kolochava village, 48°26'12"N, 23°44'00"E, 500 m a. s. l., near Biological station, 15.08.1995, 1♂ (Yu. Verves). Zaporizhzhya Region: environs of Altagir village, 46°37'33.24"N, 35°16'57.36"E, Biological station of Melitopol National Pedagogical University, meadows & bushes, 4–15.06.2008, 1♀ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Synanthropic species. Larvae in corpses, decaying animal matters, faeces; produced intestinal, urinary and cutaneous secondary and tertiary myiasis of human and different vertebrate animals. Adults are the vectors of different intestinal diseases. This fly is widely known and easily bred

laboratory insect of great medical, veterinary and forensic importance according to Faucher et al., 1999; Fischer et al., 2004; Greenberg, 1971, 1973; Knotek et al., 2005; Lord et al., 1992; Stackelberg, 1959 (Штакельберг, 1959); Vinogradova, 1984 (Виноградова, 1984); Zumpt, 1965. In Ukraine the flies were collected from the beginning of March to the middle of November with peaks in April and June in synanthropic stations, in rooms, at meadows, sandy areas and bushes (Verves, 2005c).

Calliphora (s. str.) *vomitioria* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe northwards to Norway, including British Is.; Asia: Afghanistan, China (all parts), Japan (Hokkaido, Honshu, Shikoku), Kazakhstan, Korea, Mid Asia, Mongolia, Russia (Siberia, Far East), Saudi Arabia, Syria, Transcaucasia; North Africa: Canary Is., Morocco, Tunisia. Oriental Region: China (all parts), India (Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Sikkim, Uttaranchal, West Bengal), Nepal, Pakistan (North-West Frontier Province, Northern Areas, Punjab), Philippines (Luzon I., Mindanao I.), Taiwan, Thailand. Australasian/Oceanian Region: Australia, Hawaiian Is., New Zealand. Nearctic: all parts. Neotropical Region: Cuba. Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernivtzi, Ivano-Frankivsk*, Kherson, Kyiv, Lugansk, Lviv, Poltava*, Volyn and Zakarpattya regions.

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk Region: Mshana River valley, 28°51'52"N, 24°09'28"E, 9–11.08.2006, 1♂ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv City: Berizka Lake, 50°26'17"N, 30°34'41"E, 20.09.2006, 1♂, 1♀; Chervonozyoryany Prospekt, 50°24'23"N, 30°30'34"E, at trunks of trees, 27.09.2006, 1♂; Dubky Lake, 50°28'32"N, 30°25'43"E, 27.09.2006, 1♂; Golosievsky Lakes, 50°22'30"N, 30°30'30"E, humid meadows, 21.09.2003, 1♀; *ibid.*, 28.06.2004, 1♂; Kozacha street, 50°24'01"N, 30°30'05"E, on leaves & walls, 7.07.2005, 2♀; Sonyachne Lake, 50°38'22"N, 30°38'23"E, 4.10.2006, 1♀; Vasylykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 5.07.2008, 1♂; *ibid.*, 1.10.2009, 1♀ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv Region: Bila Tserkva, Park Oleksandriya, 49°48'47"N, 30°04'09"E, 3.05.2009, 1♀ (Yu. Verves). Poltava Region: Hrabarivka village, 50°22'52"N, 32°20'39"E, meadows nr Ruda River, 15.07.2009, 1♂, 7♀ (A. Drozdovska, V. Gorobchyshyn, Yu. Verves). Zakarpattya Region: Kolochava village, 48°26'12"N, 23°44'00"E, 500 m a. s. l., near Biological station, 15–17.08.1995, 3♂, 1♀ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Larvae in corpses of vertebrate animals, faeces and other decaying animal matter; prefer dead sheep and other large carcasses, after Grunin, 1970a (Грунин, 1970a); Ozerov, 1986 (Озеров, 1986); Stackelberg, 1959 (Штакельберг, 1959). Produced secondary wound myiasis of sheep (Nielsen, 1984; Norris, Titcher, 1997; Otranto & Stewens, 2002), Guinea pig, *Cavia porcellus* (Ribbeck et al., 1975) and rarely — of man (Zumpt, 1965). Flies have a strong tendency to migrate to the alpine and subalpine zones in early summer and may stay there during the summer season in Japan and Korea (Arakawa et al., 1991). This species is not synanthropic in temporary climate (Grunin, 1972), but in subarctic conditions exhibited moderate to high synanthropy (Nuorteva, 1963). Flies rare in urban and semi-urban habitats; more abundant in wooded, shaded localities, in upland treeless areas, to 700 m a. s. l. in England and Wales (Davies, Laurence, 1992). In Ukraine the specimens of this species were collected from the beginning of

April to the end of October at meadows, sandy areas and bushes (Verves, 2005c).

Calliphora (Steringomyia) subalpina (Ringdahl, 1931)

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe: Austria, Bulgaria, Belarus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia (Karelia, Komi Republic, Leningrad, Murmansk and Voronezh regions), Serbia, Slovakia, Switzerland, Sweden, Ukraine, United Kingdom; Asia: Siberia (Altay, Chita Region, Evenkia), Russian Far East, Transcaucasus, Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, Mongolia, Korean peninsula, Japan. In Ukraine recorded from Chernivtzi, Sumy* and Volyn regions.

Material examined. Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 1♂ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Larvae develop in corpses of mammals. Adult flies are distributed in lowland areas below 200 m, mainly wooded and pastoral sites rather than arable agricultural land; in woodland and at wood edges, including old industrial sites in process of returning to scrub and woodland, in semi-urban gardens and parks; expands to higher ground in the moors to 400–500 m (Verves, 2005c).

Cynomya mortuorum (Linnaeus, 1761)

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe northwards to Norway, including British Is., Faroe Is., Novaya Zemlya and Iceland; Asia: China (Gansu, Heilongjiang, Jilin, Liaoning, Neimenggu, Ningxia, Qinghai, Shanxi, Sichuan), Japan, Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, Mongolia, Russia (Siberia, Far East), Tibet, Transcaucasia. Nearctic: Greenland, USA (Alaska). Oriental Region: China (Yunnan), Pakistan (North West Frontier). Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtzi, Crimea, Dnipropetrovsk, Ivano-Frankivsk*, Kyiv, Lugansk, Poltava*, Sumy*, Zaporizhzhya, Zhytomyr and Volyn regions.

Material examined. Ivano-Frankivsk Region: Mshana River valley, 28°51'52"N, 24°09'28"E, 9–11.08.2006, 1♂ (A. Drozdovska). Kyiv City: Lopukhovate I., 50°30'22"N, 30°33'20"E, 26.09.2008, 1♀; Sovky Ponds, 50°24'35"N, 30°30'00"E, humid meadow, 3.05.2004, 1♂ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv Region: Bila Tserkva, Park Oleksandriya, 49°48'47"N, 30°04'09"E, 3.05.2009, 1♀; Tulyntsi village, 49°49'18"N, 31°10'49"E, feather-grass steppe with bushes, 15.06.2004, 1♂ (Yu. Verves). Poltava Region: Hurbyntsi village, 50°21'36"N, 32°28'35"E, 1♂ & 1♀, in copula, 2.05.2009 (V. Gorobchysyn). Sumy Region: Vakalivschyna village, 51°01'47"N, 34°55'12"E humid meadow, 18–31.05.2006, 1♂ (O. Govorun).

Remarks. Larvae develop in dead vertebrates after Grunin, 1970a, 1972 (Грунин, 1970a, 1972); Ozerov, 1986 (Озеров, 1986), including mouse carcasses and dead ship (Davies, 1999), and fish bait, Baltic herring *Clupea harengus*, in field experiments (Nuorteva, 1972). Imago feed at meat, dead fish, faeces after Sychevskaya, 1974 (Сычевская, 1974), and on cadavers according to Ozerov, 1986 (Озеров, 1986). In Poland flying period is continued from April to November, flies are distributed in synanthropic habitats, forests, bushes, meadows and mountains to 1900

m a. s. l. Flies attracted to fungus *Phallus impudicus*, faeces, corpses, flowers of entomophilous herbage, bred from dead small animals — Scandinavian lemming (*Lemmus lemmus*), tundra vole (*Microtus oeconomus*), common shrew (*Sorex araneus*), and muldvarp (*Talpa europaea*) (Draber-Mońko, 2004). Adults were collected in May — August at meadows, in bushes and forests; rare in culturophilous landscapes (Verves, 2005c).

Lucilia (Bufolucilia) bufonivora Moniez, 1876

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe, northwards to Norway, including British Is.; Asia: China (Beijing, Gansu, Heilongjiang, Hubei, Jilin, Liaoning, Neimenggu), Kazakhstan, Russia (Siberia: Altay, Novosibirsk Region, Krasnoyarskiy Krai), Tibet, Transcaucasia; North Africa: Oriental Region: China (Hunan). Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Kyiv, Poltava*, Sumy* and Ternopil* regions.

Material examined. Kyiv City: Lisove Lake, 50°27'53"N, 30°40'34"E, 20.07.2004, 1♂ (Yu. Verves). Poltava Region: Velyki Solontsi locality, 50°14'51"N, 32°35'10"E, 13–14.07.2009, 2♂ (Yu. Verves). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 1♂ (Yu. Verves). Ternopil Region: Dnister River, 48°34'10"N, 25°38'08"E, 21.05.1986, 2♀ (S. Zhrazhevsky).

Remarks. Larvae are known as obligate parasites of anuran amphibians; female lays several tens to several hundreds eggs on the skin of hosts. 1–2 hours later the eggs hatch and the emergent maggots immediately migrate to the nasal cavities and feed on the tissues in this area, causing the death of the host within 2–3 days (Brumpt, 1933a; Hendriks, 1987 etc.). *Bufo bufo* is the preferred host after Adamiak, 1975; Brumpt, 1934; Draber-Mońko, 2004; Ewert, Traud, 1979; Garanin, Shaldybin, 1976 (Гаранин, Шалдыбин, 1976); Hesse, 1906; Hinaidy, Frey, 1990; Kordges, 2000; Moniez, 1876, 1878; Strijbosch, 1980; Weddeling, Kordges, 2008. The myiasis of *Bufo calamita* (Kordges, 2000; Vestjens, 1958; Weddeling, Kordges, 2008; Zavadil et al., 1997), *B. viridis* after Garanin, Shaldybin, 1976 (Гаранин, Шалдыбин, 1976), *Hyla arborea* (Goverse, 2007; Meisterhans, Heusser, 1970), *Pelobates fuscus* after Garanin, Shaldybin, 1976 (Гаранин, Шалдыбин, 1976), *Rana arvalis* after Garanin & Shaldybin, 1976 (Гаранин, Шалдыбин, 1976); Neumann & Meyer, 1994; Zumpt, 1965, *R. esculenta* — complex (Albrecht et al., 1996; Draber-Mońko, 2004; Kordges, 2000; Weddeling, Kordges, 2008), *R. temporaria* (Draber-Mońko, 2004; Koskela et al., 1974; Portschiński, 1899; Vogel, 1935), *Alytes obstetricans* (Kordges, 2000; Neumann, Meyer, 1994; Weddeling, Kordges, 2008) are more or less common too. The cases of myiasis of caudate amphibians (*Salamandra salamandra*, *Triturus alpestris*, *T. vulgaris*) are relatively rare (Neumann, Meyer, 1994; Zumpt, 1965). Myiasis of amphibians caused by this species has been documented in Europe between 47°20'N and 64°10'N in cool and humid regions (Zavadil, 1997). Flying activity of imago is continued from May to August (Čepelák, 1986; Draber-Mońko, 2004). In Ukraine adults were collected from the end of May to the end of August at mead-

ows, in bushes and humid forests; very rare in culturophilous landscapes (Verves, 2005c).

Lucilia (Bufolucilia) silvarum (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution. Holarctic: Europe, northwards to Norway, including British Is.; Asia: China (Gansu, Heilongjiang, Ningxia, Qinghai), Israel, Japan (all parts), Mongolia, Russia (South Siberia, Primorye), Transcaucasia; North America: Canada (Alberta), USA (Arizona, California, Louisiana, Maine, Idaho, Ohio, Oklahoma, South Carolina, Virginia, Washington, Wisconsin). Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtzi, Crimea*, Dnipropetrovsk, Ivano-Frankivsk*, Kherson, Kyiv, Lugansk, Mykolaiv, Poltava*, Sumy*, Volyn, Zakarpattia and Zaporizhzhya regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Trakhtemyriv village, 49°57'20"N, 31°22'39"E, bank of stream, 13.07.1988, 1♂ (S. Zhrazhevsky); Uman, Park Sophiivka, 48°44'29"N, 30°13'43"E, 13–14.06.2006, 4♂, 2♀ (Yu. Verves). Crimea: Beregove village, 44°54'20"N 33°37'E, sandy area, 9.08.2004, 1♂ (Yu. Verves); Kanaka gully, 44°48'N, 34°41'E, meadows, 5–8.05.2005, 1♂ (L. Khrokalo). Ivano-Frankivsk Region: Mshana River valley, 28°51'52"N, 24°09'28"E, 9–11.08.2006, 1♀ (A. Drozdovska). Kherson Region: Vynogradove village, 46°28'53"N, 32°58'05"E, 23.07.2006, 8♂ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv City: Berizka Lake, 50°26'17"N, 30°34'41"E, 22.06.2006, 2♂; Druzhby Narodiv Park, 50°30'16"N, 30°32'31"E, meadows nr lake, 8.07.2005, 5♂, 3♀; Feofania, 50°20'27"N, 30°29'20"E, mesophytic forest nr pond, 22.05.2008, 1♂, 3♀; Golosieve Park in memory Maxim Rylsky, 50°23'22"N, 30°30'00"E, 10.06.2009, 2♂; Golosievsky Lakes, 50°22'30"N, 30°30'30"E, humid meadows, 28.06.2004, 2♂; *ibid.*, 12.09.2005, 2♂, 2♀; Lisove Lake, 50°27'53"N, 30°40'34"E, 20.07.2004, 2♂; Lysa Gora hills, 50°23'42"N, 30°32'54"E, bushes, 19.08.2004, 1♀; Malynivka Lake, 50°29'11"N, 30°34'18"E, 23.06.2005, 1 male; Sonyachne Lake, 50°38'22"N, 30°38'23"E, 10.20.2006, 1♂; Sovky Ponds, 50°24'35"N, 30°30'00"E, humid meadow, 27.08.2004, 5♂; *ibid.*, 11.07.2005, 4♂; Unnamed Dnipro Island, 50°30'22"N, 30°38'23"E, 30.05.2008, 1♀; Vasylykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 7.07.2008, 1♂ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv Region: Bila Tserkva, Park Oleksandriya, 49°48'47"N, 30°04'09"E, 3.05.2009, 1♂, 1♀ (Yu. Verves); Chornobyl, 51°16'00"N, 30°13'00"E, 22.08.1989, 1♂ (S. Zhrazhevsky); Irpin, 50°31'11"N, 30°14'40"E, 15.07.1997, 1♂ (V. Gorobchyshyn); Tatsenykivka village, 50°09'16"N, 30°41'04"E, 14.09.2003, at leaves and ground at border of pine forest nr lake, 1♂; Tulyntsi village, 49°49'18"N, 31°10'49"E, feather-grass steppe with bushes, 4.06.2003, 2♂, 3♀ (Yu. Verves). Lugansk Region: Provallia village, 48°07'58"N, 39°40'02"E, 27–29.07.2008, 1♀ (A. Drozdovska). Poltava Region: Davydivka village, 50°21'55"N, 32°23'43"E, meadows, 15.07.2009, 1♂; Hrabarivka village, 50°22'52"N, 32°20'39"E, meadows nr Ruda River, 15.07.2009, 1♂; Hurbyntsi village, 50°21'36"N, 32°28'35"E, on flowering *Apiaceae*, 18–22.07.2005, 1♂, 4♀; Keybalivka village, 50°18'34"N, 32°30'10"E, meadows near Uday River, 11.07.2009, 2♂; Leliaky village, 50°19'41"N, 32°29'34"E, 21.7.2005, 4♀; Ulianivka village, 50°07'51"N, 32°33'21"E, meadows, 13.07.09, 1♀; Velyki Solontsi locality, 50°14'51"N, 32°35'10"E, 13–14.07.2009, 9♂, 3♀ (A. Drozdovska, V. Gorobchyshyn, Yu. Verves). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 20♂, 2♀ (Yu. Verves); Vakalivschyna village, 51°01'47"N, 34°55'12"E, bog, 5–14.06.2007, 1♀ (O. Govorun). Zaporizhzhya Region: environs of Altagir village, 46°37'33.24"N, 35°16'57.36"E, Biological station of Melitopol National Pedagogical University meadows & bushes, 4–15.06.2008, 3♂ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Larvae are developed in carcasses of mice (Davies, 1999) and young ducks (Brothers, 1970), and decaying meat after Brothers, 1970 and Stackelberg, 1959 (Штакельберг, 1959); sometimes in human corpses (Adair, Kondratieff, 2006). This species has been reported infesting a living rat *Rattus norvegicus* (Dodge, 1952). Maggots are

parasitized in nostrils of anuran amphibians *Bufo americanus* (Anderson, Bennett, 1963; Bleakney, 1963; Bolek, Coggins, 2002), *Bufo boreas* (Eaton et al., 2008; James, Maslin, 1947), *B. bufo* (Draber-Moňko, 2004; Martínez-Sánchez et al., 1998; Mortensen, 1892), *B. hemiophrys* (Eaton et al., 2008), *Pleurodeles waltl* (Martínez-Sánchez et al., 1998), *Rana catesbeiana* (Hall, 1948), *R. perezii* (Martínez-Sánchez et al., 1998), *R. sylvatica* (Bolek, Janovy, 2004; Eaton et al., 2008) and *Pseudacris maculata* (Eaton et al., 2008; Roberts, 1998). The adult females deposit the eggs on the anurans' backs which hatch into larvae after one or two hours. The larvae then burrow into the skin and causes lesions. The myiasis is fatal to an anuran host in general, but sometimes hosts survived infestation (Eaton et al., 2008). Flies were collected at altitudes to 3500 m o. s. l. (Adair, Kondratieff, 2006). Flying activity in Central Europe is registered in May–October (Čepelák, 1986). Flies feed on faeces, cadavers and different flowering plants (Draber-Moňko, 2004), dominant in meadows and absent in forests (Faucherre, Cherix, 1998). In Ukraine the adults were collected in May–September with peaks in the end of May and July at meadows, bushes and sandy areas; not rare in culturophilous landscapes (Verves, 2005c).

Lucilia (s. str.) ampullacea Villeneuve, 1922

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe northwards to Northern Germany, Estonia and Leningrad Region, including British Is.; Asia: Afghanistan, China (Gansu, Heilongjiang, Jilin, Liaoning, Neimenggu, Shaanxi, Shandong, Xinjiang), Japan (all parts), Kazakhstan, Korea, Mid Asia, Mongolia, Russia (Siberia and Far East), Transcaucasia; North Africa: Algeria. Oriental Region: India (Karnataka, Kerala, West Bengal), Pakistan (Punjab). Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Kyiv, Lugansk and Zakarpattia regions.

Material examined. Kyiv City: Baykove Cementery, 50°25'02"N, 30°30'37"E, 16.08.2004, 1♂; Berizka Lake, 50°26'17"N, 30°34'41"E, 22.06. — 20.09.2006, 5♂, 2♀; Feofania, 50°20'27"N, 30°29'20"E, mesophytic forest nr pond, 22.05.2008, 1♂; Sovky Ponds, 50°24'35"N, 30°30'00"E, humid meadow, 27.08.2004, 2♂; Unnamed Dnipro Island, 50°30'22"N, 30°38'23"E, 29.08.2008, 1♀; Vasylykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 5.07.2008, 1♂; *ibid.*, 28.05. & 2.10.2009, 2♂ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Larvae develop in dead fish, birds, mammals after Ozerov, 1986 (Озеров, 1986), e. g. dead mice and quails (Smith, Wall, 1997), produced facultative cutaneous myiasis of squirrel (*Glis glis*) (Heim de Balsac, 1937), hedgehog (*Erinaceus europaeus*) (Nielsen et al., 1978), turtles *Testudo graeca* (Principato, Cioffi, 1996) and *T. hermanni* (Hinaidy, Frey, 1984). Imago attracted to dead fish and animals after Ozerov, 1986 (Озеров, 1986), and flowering plants (Draber-Moňko, 2004); often at windows of buildings according to Petrova, Soboleva, 1973 (Петрова, Соболева, 1973). In Mid Europe flight activity was registered in May — October (Čepelák, 1986; Draber-Moňko, 2004). In Ukraine flies were collected from the middle of July to the beginning of October at meadows, dry bog and in forests; not rare in synanthropic habitats (Verves, 2005c).

***Lucilia* (s. str.) *caesar* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe, northwards to Norway, including British Is.; Asia: Afghanistan, China (all parts), Iran, Israel, Japan (all parts), Kazakhstan, Korea, Mid Asia, Mongolia, Syria, Turkey, Russia (Siberia, Far East), Transcaucasia; North Africa: Algeria, Canary Is., Egypt, Morocco. Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtzi, Crimea, Donetsk, Kharkiv, Khmelnyzky, Kherson, Kyiv, Lugansk, Lviv, Odesa, Poltava, Sumy*, Ternopil, Vinnytzya, Volyn, Zakarpattia, Zaporizhzhya and Zhytomyr Regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Uman, Park Sophiivka, 48°44'29"N, 30°13'43"E, 11.06.2005, 3 ♂, 1 ♀; *ibid.*, 13–14.06.2006, 4 ♂, 2 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Kherson Region: Chornomorsky Nature Reserve, 46°20'N, 31°57'E, Solenoozerny branch, coast of sea, 28.07.2006, 1 ♀; Vynogradove village, 46°28'53"N, 32°58'05"E, 23.07.2006, 4 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv City: Baykove Cemetery, 50°25'02"N, 30°30'37"E, 16.08.2004, 4 ♂, 1 ♀; Berizka Lake, 50026'17"N, 30034'41"E, 22.06. — 20.09.2006, 17 ♂, 10 ♀; Chervonozoryany Prospekt, 50024'23"N, 30030'34"E, Eat trunks of trees, 27.09.2006, 1 ♂; Druzhby Narodiv Park, 50°30'16"N, 30°32'31"E, meadows nr Lake, 8.07.2005, 3 ♂; Dubky Lake, 50028'32"N, 30025'43"E, 27.09.2006, 6 ♂, 5 ♀; Feofania, 50°20'27"N, 30°29'20"E, mesophitic forest nr pond, 22.05.2008, 2 ♂, 1 ♀; Golosieve Park in memory Maxim Rylsky, 50°23'22"N, 30°30'00"E, 10.06.2009, 20 ♂, 2 ♀; Golosievsky Lakes, 50°22'30"N, 30°30'30"E, humid meadows, 21.09.2003, 1 ♂; *ibid.*, 28.06.2004, 1 ♂; *ibid.*, 12.09.2005, 2 ♂; Kozacha street, 50°24'01"N, 30°30'05"E, on leaves & walls, 7.07.2005, 9 ♂; *ibid.*, 22.06.2009, 1 ♂; Kyiv-Pechersk Lavra, 50°26'06"N, 30°33'26"E, bushes at hills, 21.05.2009, 2 ♂; Lisove Lake, 50°27'53"N, 30°40'34"E, 20.07.2004, 4 ♂; Lysa Gora hills, 50°23'42"N, 30°32'54"E, bushes, 19.08.2004, 2 ♂; Malynivka Lake, 50°29'11"N, 30°34'18"E, 23.06.2005, 1 ♂; Sonyachne Lake, 50°38'22"N, 30°38'23"E, 4.10.2006, 3 ♂, 1 ♀; Unnamed Dnipro Island, 50°30'22"N, 30°38'23"E, 30.05. — 27.06.2008, 8 ♂, 1 ♀; Verbne Lake, 50°29'24"N, 30°31'11"E, 31.08.2004, 1 ♂, 2 ♀; Sovky Ponds, 50°24'35"N, 30°30'00"E, humid meadow, 27.08.2004, 3 ♂; *ibid.*, 11.07.2005, 1 ♂; Syretz, humid meadow nr pond, 15.07.2005, 7 ♂, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves); Uralska street, 50°23'37"N, 30°31'30"E, 3–6.07.2009, 6 ♂ (A. Drozdovska); Vasylykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 25.06. — 8.08.2008, 9 ♂, 2 ♀; 18.05. — 5.10.2009, 29 ♂, 6 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv Region: Bila Tserkva, Park Oleksandriya, 49°48'47"N, 30°04'09"E, 3.05.2009, 1 ♂; Irpin River, 50°31'05"N, 30°15'33"E, forest near bog, 26.04.2003, 1 ♂, 2 ♀; Tatsensky village, 50°09'16"N, 30°41'04"E, 14.09.2003, at leaves and ground at border of pine forest nr lake, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves); Pustovarivka village, 49°42'03"N, 29°49'44"E, 26–27.06.2004, 1 ♂ (A. Drozdovska). Odesa Region: Kyslytsia village, 45°24'53"N, 29°02'41"E, 7–9.08.2009, 1 ♀ (V. Gorobchyshyn). Poltava Region: Davydivka village, 50°21'55"N, 32°23'43"E, meadows, 15.07.2009, 1 ♀; Hrabarivka village, 50°22'52"N, 32°20'39"E, meadows nr Ruda River, 15.07.2009, 3 ♂, 1 ♀; Keybalivka village 50°18'34"N, 32°30'10"E, meadows near Uday River, 14.07.2009, 1 ♂; Leliaky village, 50°19'41"N, 32°29'34"E, 21.7. 2005, 1 ♀ (A. Drozdovska, V. Gorobchyshyn, Yu. Verves). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 19 ♂, 2 ♀ (Yu. Verves); Vakalivschyna village, 51°01'47"N, 34°55'12"E, bog, 5–14.06.2007, 1 ♂ (O. Govorun). Zaporizhzhya Region: environs of Altagir village, 46°37'33.24"N, 35°16'57.36"E, Biological station of Melitopol National Pedagogical University, meadows & bushes, 4–15.06.2008, 5 ♂ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Larvae usually develop in corpses of great mammals: pig, sheep etc (Grassberger & Frank, 2004), rarely — in small carcasses of rodents: Chinese Striped Hamster (*Cricetulus barabensis*) after Artamonov, 1997 (Apramonov, 1997), mice (Davies, 1999), and birds: quail, *Coturnix coturnix* (Smith & Wall, 1997). Occasionally larval development takes place in soiled and wet fleece (Otranto & Stewens, 2002). Larvae produce facultative primary cutaneous and subcutaneous myiasis (so called "strikes") of hu-

mans (Franza et al., 2006; James, 1947; Zumpt, 1965), sheep (Brinkmann, 1976; Hall, 1997; Hall, Farkas, 2000; Minář et al., 1975; Nielsen, 1984; Norris, Titcher, 1997; Stevens, Wall, 1997; Wall et al., 1992a, b), including Ukraine territory after Goncharov, 1975 (Гончаров, 1975), feral cat (*Felis catus*) (Supperer & Hinaidy, 1987), livestock (Ribbeck et al., 1987), hedgehog (*Erinaceus europaeus*) (Draber-Moňko, 2004), and aural myiasis of rabbits (Principato, Cioffi, 1996). Five cases of asthma and rhinoconjunctivitis following exposure to larvae were observed still in 19th century: three had work-related asthma as they were working on a fish bait farm or shop and two had asthma when they went fishing (Siracusa et al., 1889). Maggots formerly were used in the treatment of chronic osteomyelitis (Baer, 1931). Imago attracted by faeces, dung, carcasses (Park, 1977); feed at flowers of different plants, excreta of homopters (Draber-Moňko, 2004; Verves, 2003) and attracted by mushroom *Phallus impudicus* (Fischer, Vicha, 2003). Adult flies are more common in villages than urban areas (Hwang, Turner, 2005) and prefer lowland and mountains forests (Kano, Shinonaga, 1968; Mitsui, 2002) to altitudes about 2500 m a. s. l. (Xue, 2006). In Ukraine adults were collected from the beginning of May to the middle of October with peak in August at meadows, in bushes and sandy areas; common in synanthropic habitats (Verves, 2005c).

***Lucilia* (s. str.) *illustris* (Meigen, 1826)**

Distribution. Holarctic: widespread to tundra zone. Oriental Region: China (Guizhou, Hunan, Jiangxi, Zhejiang); India (Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Uttaranchal); Japan: Ryukyu Is. (Amami-Oshima Is.); Myanmar; Pakistan: Punjab. Australasian/Oceanian Region: Australia. Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtzi, Crimea, Dnipropetrovsk, Donetsk, Kharkiv, Kyiv, Odesa, Poltava, Sumy*, Vinnytzya, Volyn and Zakarpattia regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Cherkasy, 49°26'00"N, 32°04'00"E, 1.06.1988, 1 ♀ (S. Zhrazhevsky); Uman, Park Sophiivka, 48°44'29"N, 30°13'43"E, 11.06.2005, 2 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv City: Berizka Lake, 50026'17"N, 30034'41"E, 20.09.2006, 1 ♂, 26 ♀; Dubky Lake, 50°28'32"N, 30°25'43"E, 15.07.2005, 1 ♂; *ibid.*, 27.09.2006, 3 ♀; Golosieve Park in memory Maxim Rylsky, 50°23'22"N, 30°30'00"E, 10.06.2009, 1 ♂; Malynivka Lake, 50°29'11"N, 30°34'18"E, 23.06.2005, 2 ♀, 1 ♂; Olzhyn I., 50°16'50"N, 30°39'20"E, 16.09.2009, 1 ♀; Unnamed Dnipro Island, 50°30'22"N, 30°38'23"E, 29.08.2008, 1 ♂; Verbne Lake, 50°29'24"N, 30°31'11"E, 31.08.2004, 1 ♂; Vasylykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 28.07.2009, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv Region: Irpin, 50°31'11"N, 30°14'40"E, 1–15.07.1997, 1 ♂ (V. Gorobchyshyn); Kozyn village, 50°13'07"N, 30°39'326"E, Kozynka River coast, bushes, 14.09.2003, 1 ♂; Tatsensky village, 50°09'16"N, 30°41'04"E, 14.09.2003, at leaves and ground at border of pine forest nr Lake, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Poltava Region: Mala Krucha village, 50°12'20"N, 32°33'26"E, 11–13.07.08, 1 ♂ (A. Drozdovska). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 5 ♂ (Yu. Verves); Vakalivschyna village, 51°01'47"N, 34°55'12"E, bog, 5–14.06.2007, 1 ♀ (O. Govorun). Zakarpattia Region: Kolochava village, 2–5 km W, 500 m a. s. l., meadows on coast of Tereblyha River, 17.08.1995, 3 ♂ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Larvae are developed in dead mammals (rabbits, rodents, sheep etc) and birds, rarely — in faeces after

Davies, 1999; Grunin, 1970a, 1975 (Грунин, 1970a, 1975); Smith, Wall, 1997; Tomberlin, Adler, 1998; have the ability to cause wound myiasis of humans (Chigusa et al., 1996; Laitinen et al., 1970), sheep (Brinkmann, 1976; Haddow, Thomson, 1937; Hall, 1997; Hall, Farkas, 2000; Nielsen, 1984; Norris, Titcher, 1997), mouflon (*Ovis aries*), argali (*O. ammon*), hedgehog (*Erinaceus europaeus*) (Draber-Moňko, 2004), raccoon (*Procyon lotor*) (Botzler, Hurley, 1979), dogs (Principato, Cioffi, 1996), fox cub (*Vulpes vulpes*) (Hall, Wall, 1995), Eurasian shrew (*Sorex araneus*), Eurasian red squirrel (*Sciurus vulgaris*), moose (*Alces alces*) after Gaponov, 1995 (Гапонов, 1995), bird *Pernis apivorus* (Accipitridae) (Hinaidy, Frey, 1990), and known as a parasite of larvae of beetle *Dictyoploca japonica* (Mizukami, 1964). Flyind activity continues from April to October in Mid Europe (Čepelák, 1986). Imago attracted by dead fish, human and animal faeces, animal carcasses, common near human dwellings (Park, 1977), feed on flowering plants (Draber-Moňko, 2004) and attracted by *Phallus impudicus* (Fischer, Vicha, 2003). The maggots are universally available and very cost effective in larval therapy (Bunkis et al., 1985; Hall, Smith, 1993; Leclercq, 1990; Sherman et al., 2000; Sherman, Petchter, 1988). The scientists worked with larvae of this species on a case where other conventional methods failed to correctly estimate the minimum time since death (Lord et al., 1992). In Ukraine flies were collected from the beginning of June to the middle of September at meadows; rare in synanthropic habitats (Verves, 2005c).

Lucilia (Phaenicia) cuprina (Wiedemann, 1830)

Distribution. According to the opinions of some dipterists (Kurahashi, Kirk-Spriggs, 2006; Zumpt, 1956b) this species is primary endemic to the Afrotropical and Madagascan regions really and probably spreads to other tropical and subtropical areas via the sheep-farming industry. This species has been distributed into some countries of Europe: Spain (Martínez-Sánchez et al., 1999; Rognes, 1993), Czech Republic: Moravia (Fischer, Vicha, 2003), South Russia: Orenburg, Volgograd and Ural regions (Grunin, 1969; Грунин, 1975), Asia northwards to Kazakhstan, South Siberia, Southern Primorye after Grunin, 1975 (Грунин, 1975) and Honshu I. from Japan (Kano, Shinonaga, 1968). This fly has occupied totally Oriental Region (James, 1966, 1977; Kano, Shinonaga, 1968; Omar et al., 2003), Australian continent, the majority of Oceanian islands (Wallman, 2001) and New Zealand (Bishop, 1993; Heath et al., 1991). In USA this species is distributed from Virginia to Florida west to Missouri and Texas and California (Whitworth, 2006). In Neotropical Region this fly have been recorded for Argentina (Mariluis, Mulieri, 2003), different states of Brazil (D'Almeida, 1986; Linhares, 1981; Oliveira et al., 1999; Pereira, Rita, 1986; Vianna et al., 1998), Colombia, Paraguay and Uruguay (Mariluis et al., 1994; Mello, 1961, 2003; Rodrigues-Guimarães et al., 2001). Firstly recorded from Ukraine.

Material examined. Odesa Region: Izmail, 45°21'06"N, 28°50'11"E, 4–8.08.2009, 1 ♂ (V. Gorobchyshyn).

Remarks. The adults of this eusynanthropic species abundantly found in and around human dwellings, especially along seashores; they feed on faeces, corpses, fallen fruit, flowers, honeydew of aphids etc. The larvae are usually developed on garbage-dump, scraps of food, faeces, dung and dead animals of different size (Kano, Shinonaga, 1968; Otranto, Stewens, 2002; Verves, Khrokalo, 2006, 2009). This species is well known as a fly that causes a short-duration (over 3–5 days) primary wood (traumatic) myiasis ("fly strike") in different domestic animals, especially sheep, rarely — camels, goats, cattle, dogs, and humans (Dallwitz, 1987; Hall, 1995, 1997; Hall, Smith, 1993). The influence of temperature on the developmental rates of eggs, larvae and pupae was examined at 19°, 27° & 35°C. The median time from egg to adult was 30.3 days at 19°C, 12.8 days at 27°C and 10.4 days at 35°C (Ash, Greenberg, 1975); The mean generation time in laboratory conditions is 19.8 days; the population parameters suggest that *L. cuprina* is r-strategist (Abou Zied et al., 2003). This species remains a major pest in Australia and up to 3 million sheep may be killed each year; it initiates more than 85% of fly strikes on sheep in Australia with an estimated average annual cost of a \$150...280 million to wool industry (Beck et al., 1985; Urech et al., 2009). Adults are vector of dermatophilosis — a chronic bacterial infection, caused by *Dermatophilus congolensis* which invades the epidermis of hosts; sheep body strike is more often associated with bacterial fleece rot, a superficial dermatitis induced by moisture and bacterial proliferation on the skin, resulting in a matted band of discoloured fleece, caused by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Gherardi et al., 1983; Wardhaugh, Dallwitz, 1984; Watts et al., 1979). Twenty eight per cent (15) of 53 workers engaged in a sheep blowfly breeding programme designed to control genetically *Lucilia cuprina* experienced allergic manifestations resulting from contact with this insect. The most common symptoms were rhinitis, affected eyes, rashes, and lower respiratory symptoms (Kaufman et al., 1989). This is one of the most important species used for forensic investigations (Carvalho, Mello-Patiu, 2008; Kurahashi, Kirk-Spriggs, 2006). In rabbit-prone areas of Australia and New Zealand, this fly is known as a vector of rabbit haemorrhagic disease virus. The implications of these results are discussed in the context of rabbit biological control (Barratt et al., 2001; Crosby, McLennan, 1996). Maggot debridement therapy of humans with larvae of this species is effective in the treatment of diabetic foot ulcers (Paul et al., 2009).

Lucilia (Phaenicia) pilosiventris Kramer, 1910

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe: Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Russia (Voroniezh Region), Slovakia, The Netherlands, Ukraine; Asia: China (Gansu, Neimenggu, Sichuan), Kazakhstan (Qostanay Province), Tibet. Ukraine:

Cherkasy, Kyiv, Lugansk, Poltava* and Zaporizhzhya regions.

Material examined. Kyiv Region: Tulyntsi village, 49°49'18"N, 31°10'49"E, feather-grass steppe with bushes, 29.05. — 5.07.2003, 2 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Poltava Region: Hurbyntsi village, 50°21'36"N, 32°28'35"E, on flowering *Apiaceae*, 18.07.2005, 2 ♂ (A. Drozdovska).

Remarks. In Poland flying period takes place from May to September; flies prefer xerophilous meadows, where feed on different flowering plants (Draber-Mońko, 2004). In Ukraine flies were collected from end of May to August in mesophytic forest, steppe and sandy areas (Verves, 2005c).

Lucilia (Phaenicia) regalis (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe: Austria, Belarus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, Hungary, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia (Kaliningrad, Udmurtia), Slovakia, Sweden, The Netherlands, Ukraine; Asia: Georgia, China (Gansu, Neimenggu, Qinghai, Sichuan), Kazakhstan (Astana Region), Mongolia, Russia (Altay, Chelyabinsk Region, Eastern Sayan, Amur Region), Tibet. In Ukraine known from Cherkasy, Kherson*, Lugansk and Rivne regions.

Material examined. Kherson Region: Chornomorsky Nature Reserve, 46°20'N, 31°57'E, Solenoozerny branch, bank of see, 27.07.2006, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Rivne Region: Vilia River, 50°32'19"N, 26°30'54"E, 17.07.1988, 1 ♀ (S. Zhrazhevsky).

Remarks. In Poland flying period takes place from May to September; flies feed on different flowering plants (Draber-Mońko, 2004), faeces; prefer humid forest borders, meadows, and bogs (Verves & Khrokalo, 2006c).

Lucilia (Phaenicia) richardsi Collin, 1926

Distribution. Palaearctic: all parts of Europe, including British Is.; Asia: Kazakhstan (Ongtustik Qazaqstan Province), Russia (Buryatia), Transcaucasia. Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtzi, Dnipropetrovsk, Kyiv, Lugansk, Poltava*, Sumy* and Zaporizhzhya regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Moshny village, 49°32'00"N, 31°45'00"E, 15.08.1984, 1 ♀ (S. Zhrazhevsky); Uman, Park Sophiivka, 48°44'29"N, 30°13'43"E, 13–14.06.2006, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv City: Golosievsky Lakes, 50°22'30"N, 30°30'30"E, humid meadows, 12.09.2005, 1 ♂; Vasylkivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 28–29.07.2009, 2 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv Region: Stugna River, 50°09'23"N, 30°44'01"E, 21.08.2004, at leaves and ground at border of pine forest nr lake, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Poltava Region: Shkuraty village, 50°12'41"N, 32°40'26"E, meadows, 17.07.2009, 3 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Larvae bred from mise carcasses (Davies, 1999) and wounds of bird European nightjar (*Caprimulgus europaeus*) (Nuorteva, 1959). Flying activity was registered in May — September (Čepelák, 1986). In Ukraine adults were collected in June — September in different meadows, forests and steppe; very rare in synanthropic localities (Verves, 2005c).

Lucilia (Phaenicia) sericata (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution. This species is widely distributed in Holarctic (not reaches tundra zone to North), Oriental and Australasian/Oceanian regions; known from some parts (probably introduced) of Afrotropical Region: Azores Is., Gough I., Lesotho, Mozambique, Namibia, Nightingale Is., Zimbabwe, South African Republic (Kurahashi, Kirk-Spriggs, 2006; Scholtz et al., 2000; Zumt, 1956b), St. Helena I., Tristan da Cunha Is. (Peris, Mora, 1991), Sudan (Baumgartner, Greenberg, 1985) and Neotropic Region: Argentina (all parts: Mariluis, 1982; Mariluis, Mulieri, 2003; Mariluis, Schnack, 2002), Brazil (Guanabara, Rio de Janeiro and Rio Grande do Sul States) (Mello, 1961, 2003; Vianna et al., 1998), Chile (Mariluis, Guarnera, 1980), Colombia (Ordóñez et al., 2008); Paraguay (Mariluis et al., 1994). Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtzi, Crimea, Dnipropetrovsk, Donetsk, Kharkiv, Kherson, Khmelnyzky, Kyiv, Lugansk, Lviv, Mykolaiv*, Odesa, Poltava, Sumy, Ternopil, Vinnytzya, Volyn, Zakarpattia, Zaporizhzhya and Zhytomyr regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Uman, Park Sophiivka, 48°44'29"N, 30°13'43"E, 13–14.06.2006, 5 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Crimea: Beregovy village, 44°54'20"N 33°37'E, sandy area, 31.07. — 11.08.2004, 22 ♂, 3 ♀ (Yu. Verves); Kanaka gully, 44°48'N, 34°41'E, meadows, 5–8.05.2005, 1 ♀ (L. Khrokalo); Karadagh Nature Reserve, 44°55'53"N, 35°13'22"E, 3.07.2006, 1 ♂ (A. Drozdovska); Kazantip Nature Reserve, 45°28'N, 35°50'E, 10–13.05.2005, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (L. Khrokalo & A. Kotenko); *ibid.*, 19–29.07.2007, 25 ♂, 6 ♀ (Yu. Verves); Sevastopol, 44°37'30"N, 33°33'E, Striletzka Bay, 22–23.08.2005, 1 ♂ (V. Gorobchshyn). Kherson Region: Chornomorsky Nature Reserve, 46°20'N, 31°57'E, Rybalchansky branch, near living buildings, 24–25.07.2006, 3 ♂, 2 ♀; *ibid.*, Solenoozerny branch, bank of see, 28–30.07.2006, 5 ♂, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves); Novooleksandrivka village, 46°19'44"N, 32°28'43"E, near pig farm, at horse dung, 4.09.1961, 6 ♂, 1 ♀; *ibid.*, dust hole, at destroyed melon, 5.09.1961, 37 ♂, 2 ♀; *ibid.*, near poultry farm, at horse an pig dung, 5.09.1961, 14 ♂, 5 ♀; *ibid.*, near pig farm, at pig dung, 6.09.1961, 38 ♂ (O. Viktorov-Nabokov). Kyiv City: Baykove Cementery, 50°25'02"N, 30°30'37"E, 16.08.2004, 11 ♂; Chervonozoryany Prospekt, 50°24'23"N, 30°30'34", Eat trunks of trees, 27.09.2006, 1 ♀; Druzhby Narodiv Park, 50°30'16"N, 30°32'31"E, meadows nr Lake, 8.07.2005, 1 ♂; Dubky Lake, 50°28'32"N, 30°25'43"E, 15.07.2005, 3 ♂, 1 ♀; *ibid.*, 27.09.2006, 4 ♂, 1 ♀; Golosieve Park in memory Maxim Rylsky, 50°23'22"N, 30°30'00"E, 10.06.2009, 1 ♂; Golosievsky Lakes, 50°22'30"N, 30°30'30"E, humid meadows, 12.09.2005, 3 ♀; Kozacha street, 50°24'01"N, 30°30'05"E, on leaves & walls, 7.07.2005, 3 ♂, 1 ♀; Kyiv-Pechersk Lavra, 50°26'06"N, 30°33'26"E, 21.05.2009, bushes at hills, 2 ♂; Lysa Gora hills, 50°23'42"N, 30°32'54"E, bushes, 19.08.2004, 1 ♂; Redkino Lake, 50°32'25"N, 30°28'40"E, 4.07.2004, 1 ♂; Sonyachne Lake, 50°38'22"N, 30°38'23"E, 10.2006, 2 ♂; Sovky Ponds, 50°24'35"N, 30°30'00"E, humid meadow, 27.08.2004, 1 ♂; Unnamed Dnipro Island, 50°30'22"N, 30°38'23"E, 29.08.2008, 3 ♂; Verbne Lake, 50°29'24"N, 30°31'11"E, 21.04.2004, 1 ♂; *ibid.*, 31.08.2004, 5 ♂, 1 ♀; Vasylkivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 5.05. — 8.08.2008, 12 ♂, 8 ♀; *ibid.*, 18.05. — 2.10.2009, 8 ♂, 3 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv Region: Irpin, 50°31'11"N, 30°14'40"E, 1–15.07.1997, 1 ♂ (V. Gorobchshyn). Odesa Region: Izmail, 45°21'06"N, 28°50'11"E, 4–8.08.2009, 2 ♂, 1 ♀ (V. Gorobchshyn). Poltava Region: Keybalivka village 50°18'34"N, 32°30'10"E, meadows near Uday River, 12.07.2009, 1 ♂ (Yu. Protzenko); Pyratyn, 50°15'N, 32°32'E, 24.07.1989, 1 ♂ (S. Zhrazhevsky). Mykolaiv Region: Parutyn village, 46°42'24"N, 31°53'48"E, bank of sea, 15–16.07.2006, 2 ♂, 1 ♀; *ibid.*, debris of antic Olvia, 46°41'18"N, 31°53'14"E, 16.07.2006, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Rivne Region: Rivne, 50°37'N, 26°15'E, 23.05.1989, 1 ♂ (S. Zhrazhevsky). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, at wooden fences, 8–11.05.2009, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Vinnytzya Region: Illintsi, 49°05'59"N, 29°11'59"E, 24.08.1989, 1 ♀ (S. Zhrazhevsky). Zakarpattia Region: Kolochava village, 48°26'12"N, 23°44'00"E, 500 m a. s. l., near Biological

station, 15. — 1708.1995, 2 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Zaporizzhya Region: environs of Altagir village, 46°37'33.24"N, 35°16'57.36"E, Biological station of Melitopol National Pedagogical University meadows & bushes, 23.08.1997, 3 ♂, 3 ♀; *ibid.*, 4–15.06.2008, 12 ♂, 1 ♀; Berdyans'k, sandy spit on Azov Sea, 14–17.08.1994, 13 ♂, 10 ♀ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Eusynanthropic species (Mariluis, Schnack, 1996; Verves, Khrokalo, 2006, 2009). The potential fertility of one female is more than about 2300 eggs (MacKerras, 1933); one oviposition contains about 200 eggs (Cragg, 1955). Larvae necrophages, prefer the birds' and mammals' corpses of small size (Davies, 1999; Smith, Wall, 1997; Wells, Greenberg, 1994a, b), but sometimes are developed in sheep, bovine, pig and human corpses (Carvalho, Mello-Patiu, 2008; Grassberger, Frank, 2004), soiled and wet fleece (Otranto, Stewens, 2002), and coprophagous, especially bred from human faces after Petrova & Soboleva, 1973 (Петрова, Соболева, 1973), lavatories according to Sychevskaya, 1970 (Сычевская, 1970), garbage (Brothers, 1999), sheep, cattle and horse dung (Bishop, 1998). The median time from egg to adult (development at fresh macerated liver in laboratory conditions) was 53.9 days at 19°C, 13.5 days at 27°C and 11.3 days at 35°C. This species developed at a slower rate with more variability at each stage and tended to diapause at both low and high temperatures. These eurythermal features and ability to diapause have probably enabled this species to become established in cooler temperate regions (Ash, Greenberg, 1975). Adult larvae and pupae overwinter in soil (Bale, 1987; Pitts, Wall, 2004, 2005). In England, flying period from 6–20.05 to the end of August, with peak in July, and 4 generations would have been expected, with peak abundance achieved by the 4th generation at about 10th of September (Wall et al., 1993). Larvae produced the primary and secondary cutaneous myiasis of humans in all parts of areal (Bauch et al., 1984; Bednarikova, Lejska, 1977; Chigusa et al., 1996, 1998, 2000; Daniel et al., 1994; Granz et al., 1975; Greenberg, 1984; Haarlov, 1985; Hall & Wall, 1995; Khan, Khan, 1984; Mariluis, Guarnera, 1980; Rognes, 1991, 2002; Yoneda et al., 1998; Zumpt, 1965). The myiasis are favored by the patient had conditions, lack of hygiene, poor nutrition, long in-bed permanence, and the outcome of trophic ulcerative lesions with unpleasant small exudates (Guarnera, Mariluis, 1986; Hall, 1995; Ioli et al., 1997; Khan, Khan, 1987;). Similar myiasis were registered for sheep after Adamkiewicz-Depczyk, Depczyk, 1980; Baumgartner, Greenberg, 1985; Brinkmann, 1976; Cole, 1996; Davies, 1934; Domatzky, 1984 (Доматцкий, 1984); Haddow, Thomson, 1937; Hall, 1997; Hall, Farkas, 2000; Hall, Smith, 1993; Hall, Wall, 1995; Heath, Bishop, 1995; Kurahashi, Chowanadisai, 2001; Liebisch et al., 1983; Linden, Thomas, 1992; MacLeod, 1937, 1943a, b; Norris, Titcher, 1997; Snoep et al., 2002; Soler-Cruz, 2000), goats (Heath, Bishop, 1986, 1989, 1995), Nubian ibexes (*Capra ibex nubiana*), gazelles (*Gazella gazella*) (Yeruham et al., 1999), dogs, cats (Hinaidy, Frey, 1984; Principato, Cioffi, 1996; Ribbeck et al., 1974), rabbits (Hall, 1997), Guinea pigs (*Cavia porcellus*) (Hinaidy, Niebayer, 1979; Ribbeck et al., 1975), Norway rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) (Hinaidy, Frey, 1982), European

rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) (Hinaidy, Niebayer, 1979), hedgehogs (*Erinaceus europaeus*) (Hinaidy, Frey, 1984), geese (Farkas et al., 2001), turkey (Al-Khalili, Shareef, 1985), short-eared owl (*Asio flammeus*) (Frey, Hinaidy, 1978), long-eared owl (*Asio otus*), Eurasian eagle owl (*Bubo bubo*), Eurasian tawny owl (*Strix aluco*), common kestrel (*Falco tinnunculus*), griffon vulture (*Gyps fulvus*), honey buzzard (*Pernis apivorus*), marsh harrier (*Circus aeruginosus*), white stork (*Ciconia ciconia*) (Hinaidy, Frey, 1982, 1984, 1990), toad *Bufo* sp. (Stewart, Foote, 1974). The larva is primarily a scavenger, although in subtropical countries, the parasitic habit becomes strongly developed; in Africa and Australia this fly — one of serious pest intimately connected with the blowing of wool, but this fly seems to be comparatively harmless in temperate countries (Kurahashi, 1987). In England and Wales the larvae of this fly produced 500.000 myiasis of sheep ("blowfly strike") annually, of a national flock of 30 million (1.7 % infested); a questionnaire survey of sheep farmers showed that in 1989–1990 blowfly strike affected over 80% of farms, where an average of 1.5% of sheep were struck each year (French et al., 1992). Attack by larvae, if untreated rapidly leads to death of sheep from chronic ammonia toxicity (Guerrini, 1988, 1997). A single, artificially-induced fly-strike was associated with a rapid decline in food intake in sheep with a consequent reduction in liveweight. Loss of weight ranged from 0.5 to 5.5 kg over 4 to 6 days and recovery to pre-infestation liveweight took 3 to 36 days (Heath et al., 1987). In Ukraine myiasis produced by this species affected 0.26–0.65% of sheep in wooded zone, 0.1–0.4% in steppe zone, with 27–32% mortality among affected sheep; as a result, 0.1–0.7% of sheep infected in general after Mashkei, 1990 (Машкей, 1990). Adult flies distributed at borders of forests, meadows; prefer open grass coenoses (Smith, Wall, 1997, 1998); widely found in and around human dwellings; commonly found in market sections of food in cities and villages, especially near coast, attracted on fruits, flowers, decay meat, animal carcasses, human and animal faeces after Draber-Mońko, 2004; Feng, 2007; Kurahashi, 1987; Ozerov, 1986 (Озеров, 1986); Park, 1977; Petrova, Soboleva, 1973 (Петрова, Соболева, 1973); Sychevskaya, 1970 (Сычевская, 1970). Flying period is continued from April to October in Fennoscandia (Rognes, 1991) and full year in Israel (Rognes, 2002). Adults are the vectors of different intestinal diseases: especially, the adult flies are vectors of *Entamoeba coli*, *Giardia lamblia*, eggs of *Taenia* sp. (Mariluis, 1999a). This species appear to represent the heaviest potential sanitary risk with the Mihalyi's danger-index value ($p < 0.10$; $D = 15.54, 16.88$ and 12.49 respectively) (Maldonado, Centeno, 2003). This species widely known and easily bred laboratory insect and has great medical, veterinary and forensic importance: Carvalho, Mello-Patiu, 2008; Fischer et al., 2004; Grassberger, Reiter, 2001; Greenberg, 1971, 1973; Povolný, Rozsypal, 1968; Stackelberg, 1959 (Штакельберг, 1959). Sterile larvae have been used to heal chronically purulent wounds. Maggots are universally available and very cost effective

in larval therapy in military and survival medicine (Brumpt, 1933b; Craig, 1988; Hall, 1995; Mumcuoglu, 2001, 2003; Mumcuoglu et al., 1996; Scavee et al., 2003; Stewart, 1934; Wainwright, 1988), especially for the treatment of chronic osteomyelitic (Baer, 1931; Livingston, 1937). The therapeutic products of maggots include allantoin, urea, ammonium bicarbonate (Bunkis et al., 1985), phenylacetic acid and phenylacetaldehyde (Erdmann, Khalil, 1986), and bactericidal proteins secreted by *Proteus mirabilis*; two of the latter, originally named mirabilicides (Greenberg, 1968). This species is used for biological control of feral rabbits in New Zealand: flies would be likely to transit rabbit haemorrhagic disease virus to healthy rabbits by 2 methods: direct-contact: transferring virus from infested to uninfested rabbits; and indirect-contact vectors: transferring virus via rabbit forage (Barratt et al., 2001; Crosby, McLennan, 1996).

Angioneura acerba (Meigen, 1838)

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe up to Sweden to North, including British islands. Ukraine: Chernigiv & Kyiv regions.

Material examined. Kyiv City: Vasykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 27.07.2009, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves)

Remarks. Adult flies prefer forest habitats; flying period was registered from March to October (Verves, 2005c).

Angioneura fimbriata (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Hungary, Latvia, Poland, Romania, Russia (Leningrad & Tambov regions), Slovakia, Switzerland. Ukraine: Cherkasy and Chernigiv regions, Kyiv City.

Material examined. Kyiv City: Vasykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 18.06.2009, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. In Poland this species was collected from May to September at meadows and dry pastures (Draber-Mońko, 2004).

Melinda viridicyanea (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe, including British Is.; Asia: China (Xinjiang), Israel, Kazakhstan, Mid-Asia, Syria; North Africa: Morocco. Ukraine: known from Cherkasy, Chernivtzi, Chernigiv, Crimea, Ivano-Frankivsk, Poltava*, Sumy* & Zakarpattia regions.

Material examined. Poltava Region: Keybalivka village, 50°18'34"N, 32°30'10"E, meadows nr Uday River, 11. & 15.07.2009, 2 ♂, 1 ♀; Shkuraty village, 50°12'41"N, 32°40'26"E, meadows, 17.07.2009, 2 ♀; Usivka village, 50°19'52"N, 32°31'47"E, meadows, 10 & 16.07.2009, 1 ♀; Velyki Solontsi locality, 50°14'51"N, 32°35'10"E, 13–14.07.2009, 9 ♂, 3 ♀ (A. Drozdovska, V. Gorobchshyn, Yu. Verves); Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Larvae develop in living snails *Ceruella virgata*, *Discus rotundatus*, *Helicella itala* (Keilin, 1915, 1919). Imago feed at excreta of aphids *Chaitophorus capreae*, and at flowers of different plants (Draber-Mońko,

2004). Adults have been collected at humid meadows from March to October (Verves, 2005c).

Morinia doronici (Scopoli, 1763)

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe: Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Russia (Leningrad Region), Poland, Slovakia, Switzerland, Sweden, Ukraine.

In Ukraine recorded from Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Kyiv and Sumy* regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Moshny village, 49°32'00"N, 31°45'00"E, 19.06.1988, 1 ♀ (S. Zhrazhevsky). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. A pupa was found in decaying wood (Rognes, 1991a). Flying period continues from May to September (Pape et al., 2001). Flies were observed in mesophytic grass coenoses and forests after Stackelberg, 1962 (Штакельберг, 1962) and Draber-Mońko, 1989.

Pollenia amentaria (Scopoli, 1763)

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe, including British Is.; Asia: Afghanistan, Transcaucasia, Turkey; North Africa: Azores, Canary Is., Morocco. Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtzi, Kherson*, Kyiv, Lviv*, Poltava*, Sumy, Volyn and Zakarpattia regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Denhy village, 49°36'13"N, 32°10'36"E, 14.04.1989, 1 ♀; Trakhtemyriv village, 49°57'20"N, 31°22'39"E, 13.07.1988, 3 ♂ (S. Zhrazhevsky); Uman, Park Sophiivka, 48°44'29"N, 30°13'43"E, 13–14.06.2006, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Kherson Region: Vynogradove village, 46°28'53"N, 32°58'05"E, 12.07.2006, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Kirovograd Region: Vasylivka, 48°50'20"N, 33°17'03"E, 18.06.1989, 1 ♀ (S. Zhrazhevsky). Kyiv City: Dubky Lake, 50°28'32"N, 30°25'43"E, 27.09.2006, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves); Lukyanivka, 50°28'N, 30°27'E, 21.09.1948, 1 ♀ (E. Savchenko); Uralska street, 50°23'37"N, 30°31'30"E, 3–6.07.2009, 3 ♀ (A. Drozdovska); Vasykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 25.06.2008, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv Region: Irpin, 50°31'11"N, 30°14'40"E, 1–15.07.1997, 1 ♀ (V. Gorobchshyn); Svitank village, 49°52'15"N, 31°42'55"E, 4.06.1989, 1 ♂ (S. Zhrazhevsky); Tulyntsi village, 49°49'18"N, 31°10'49"E, feather-grass steppe with bushes, 4.06.2003, 5 ♂; *ibid.*, 5.07.2007, 7 ♂, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Lviv Region: Unnamed channel, 50°27'41"N, 24°17'30"E, steppe meadow, 18.07.1989, 1 ♀ (S. Zhrazhevsky). Poltava Region: Davydivka village, 50°21'55"N, 32°23'43"E, meadows, 15.07.2009, 21 ♂; Hrabarivka village, 50°22'52"N, 32°20'39"E, meadows nr Ruda River, 15.07.2009, 150 ♂, 7 ♀ *ibid.*, Hurbyntsi village, 50°21'36"N, 32°28'35"E, on flowering *Apiaceae*, 18–22.07.2005, 6 ♂; Keybalivka village 50°18'34"N, 32°30'10"E, meadows near Uday River, 11. & 17.07.2009, 3 ♂; Kroty village, 50°23'12"N, 32°28'09"E, 8.07.08, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; Leliaky village, 50°19'41"N, 32°29'34"E, bank of Uday River, 17, 19 & 21.07.2005, 24 ♂, 17 ♀; 15.07.2009, as prey of *Oxybelus trispinosus*, 1 ♂; Marynivka village, 9.07.08, 3 ♂; Shkuraty village, 50°12'41"N, 32°40'26"E, meadows, 17.07.2009, 5 ♂, 1 ♀; Ulyanivka village, meadows, 13.07.09, 1 ♂; Usivka village, 50°19'52"N, 32°31'47"E, meadows, 10 & 16.07.2009, 1 ♂; Velyki Solontsi locality, 50°14'51"N, 32°35'10"E, 13–14.07.2009, 13 ♂, 4 ♀; Zhovtne village, 50°09'30"N, 32°33'08"E, meadows, 13.07.09, 2 ♂ (A. Drozdovska, V. Gorobchshyn, Yu. Protzenko, Yu. Verves). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 9 ♂, 8 ♀ (Yu. Verves); Vakalivschyna village, 51°01'47"N, 34°55'12"E, humid meadows, 18–31.05.2006, 2 ♂; *ibid.*, bog, 5–14.06.2007, 1 ♂ (O. Govorun).

Remarks. In Poland flying period is continued from March to November; imago prefer xerothermic meadows and pine

forests; adult flies feed at excreta of homopters *Anoecia corni* and flowers of different plants (Draber-Mońko, 2004). In Ukraine adults have been collected from the end of April to the middle of September. Flies prefer meadows, steppes, sandy areas; rare in synanthropic localities (Verves, 2005c).

Pollenia angustigena Wainwright, 1940

Distribution. Holarctic: Europe: Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, The Netherlands, Ukraine, United Kingdom; North Africa: Madeira I.; North America: Canada (British Columbia, Ontario, Quebec), USA (California, Idaho, Michigan, Nevada, New York, New Jersey, Ohio, Utah, Virginia, Washington, Wisconsin). Ukraine: Cherkasy, Kyiv, Mykolaiv*, Poltava*, Sumy*, Zakarpattya and Zhytomyr* regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Tubiltsi village, 48°44'29"N, 30°13'43"E, 05.08.1988, 1 ♀ (S. Zhrazhevsky). Kyiv City: Dubky Lake, 50°28'32"N, 30°25'43"E, 27.09.2006, 2 ♀; Golosieve Park in memory Maxim Rylsky, 50°23'22"N, 30°30'00"E, 10.06.2009, 17 ♂ (Yu. Verves); Kyiv, 50°27'70"N, 30°31'86"E, 5.06.1988 (S. Zhrazhevsky). Kyiv Region: Irpin, 50°31'11"N, 30°14'40"E, 1–15.07.1997, 2 ♂ (V. Gorobchyshyn); Oseschyna village, 50°34'33"N, 30°32'26"E, coast of lake, meadows, 3.06.2007, 7 ♂, 2 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Mykolaiv Region: Parutyn village, 46°42'24"N, 31°53'48"E, bank of sea, 15–16.07.2006, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Poltava Region: Hrabarivka village, 50°22'52"N, 32°20'39"E, meadows nr Ruda River, 15.07.2009, 1 ♂; Keybalivka village, 50°18'34"N, 32°30'10"E, meadows near Uday River, 14.07.2009, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Romanka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 2 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Zhytomyr Region: Polissya Nature Reserve, 44°54'N, 35°11'E, 13–17.07.2007, 2 ♂, 2 ♀ (O. Moroz).

Remarks. Larvae bred from living lumbricids *Allolobophora caliginosa*, *A. chlorotica*, *Eisenia rosea*, *Lumbricus terrestris* (Thomson, Davies, 1973). In Southern Europe flying period is continued from March to October, with peak in early spring; imago captured during the winter months too. This species distributed at altitudes to 1200 m (Rognes, 1987b, 1991). Flies were collected from the beginning of April to the end of October at meadows and in synanthropic habitats (Verves, 2005c).

Pollenia atramentaria (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe: Andorra, Austria, Belarus', Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Georgia, Germany, Italy, Lithuania, Poland, Russia, Slovakia, Switzerland, The Netherlands, Ukraine; Asia: Armenia, Azerbaijan; North Africa: Algeria. Ukraine: Cherkasy, Kyiv and Poltava* regions.

Material examined. Kyiv City: Baykove Cemetery, 50°25'02"N, 30°30'37"E, 16.08.2004, 1 ♀; Chervonozoryany Prospekt 130, indoor of flat, 14.06.2005, 1 ♂; *ibid.*, 20.06.2009, 1 ♀; Golosievsky Lakes, 50°22'30"N, 30°30'30"E, humid meadows, 28.06.2004, 1 ♀; Kozacha street, 50°24'01"N, 30°30'05"E, on walls of buildings, 7.07.2005, 1 ♂; *ibid.*, 22.06.2009, 1 ♀; Vasylykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 23.06. — 18.07.2008, 2 ♂, 2 ♀ (Yu. Verves); Uralska street, 50°23'37"N, 30°31'30"E, 3–6.07.2009, 1 ♂ (A. Drozdovska). Kyiv Region: Irpin, 50°31'11"N, 30°14'40"E, 1–15.07.1997, 2 ♂ (V. Gorobchyshyn); Pustovarivka village, 49°42'03"N, 29°49'44"E, 26–27.06.2004, 2 ♀ (A. Droz-

dovska). Poltava Region: Leliaky village, 50°19'41"N, 32°29'34"E, 21.07.2005, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Drozdovska).

Remarks. Larvae bred from isopods *Oniscus asellus* (Séguy, 1941); probably misidentification of fly species. In Poland flying period is continued from April to October. Flies feed at excreta of homopterans *Pterocomma populeum*, *Tuberculoides annulatus* and flowers of different plants (Draber-Mońko, 2004). In Ukraine flies were collected from the end of March to the end of August with peak in April-May in synanthropic habitats generally; adult flies concentrated in buildings for wintering (Verves, 2005c).

Pollenia dasypoda Portschinskiy, 1881

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe: Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia (Lipetzki Region, North Caucasus), Slovakia, Ukraine; Asia: Arabic states, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iran, Israel, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Lebanon, Syria, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan, West Bank; North Africa: Egypt. Oriental Region: Pakistan. Ukraine: Chernivtzi, Crimea, Dnipropetrovsk, Kherson, Kyiv and Odesa* regions.

Material examined. Crimea: Kalinino village, 45°35'28"N, 34°13'25"E, meadow, 6.06.1989, 1 ♂ (L. Kurasa). Odesa Region: Suvorove village, 45°35'08"N, 28°59'00"E, 20–23.08.2009, 1 ♂ (V. Gorobchyshyn).

Remarks. A parasite of the earth worm, *Allolobophora caliginosa*; female deposits about 350 (137...531) eggs at ground surface. Larvae find the host underground and enter in it between segments (Tawfik, El-Husseini, 1971). In Poland flies were collected in July and August in forests and parks (Draber-Mońko, 2004). In Ukraine flies were collected from the end of March to the end of September at meadows and in synanthropic habitats (Verves, 2005c).

Pollenia griseotomentosa (Jacentkovsky, 1944)

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe: Andorra, Belarus', Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Russia (Ivanovo and Leningrad regions); Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, The Netherlands, Ukraine, United Kingdom; Asia: Georgia. Nearctic: Canada (Ontario), USA (Maine, Washington, Wisconsin). Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtzi, Crimea, Khmelnyzky, Kyiv, Poltava*, Zakarpattya and Zhytomyr* regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Denhy village, 49°36'13"N, 32°10'36"E, 14.04.1989, 1 ♀; Kaniv Nature Reserve, 49°43'04"N, 31°29'52"E, meadow, 31.05.1988, 1 ♀; Moshny village, 49°32'00"N, 31°45'00"E, 19.06.1988, 3 ♀; Tubiltsi village, 49°34'12"N, 31°40'48"E, 13.04.1986, 1 ♀ (S. Zhrazhevsky). Khmelnyzky Region: Chorna village, 48°56'24"N, 26°28'14"E, 15.07.1989, 1 ♀ (S. Zhrazhevsky). Kyiv City: Baykove Cemetery, 50°25'02"N, 30°30'37"E, 16.08.2004, 2 ♂; Dubky Lake, 50°28'32"N, 30°25'43"E, 15.07.2005, 1 ♀; Lisove Lake, 50°27'53"N, 30°40'34"E, 20.07.2004, 1 ♂; Sovky Ponds, 50°24'35"N, 30°30'00"E, humid meadow, 3.05.2004, 2 ♀; *ibid.*, 11.07.2005, 5 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Poltava Region: Keybalivka village 50°18'34"N, 32°30'10"E, meadows near Uday River, 14. & 18.07.2009, 2 ♂, 1 ♀; Leliaky village, 50°19'41"N, 32°29'34"E, 21.7. 2005, 1 ♂; Shkuraty village, 50°12'41"N, 32°40'26"E, meadows, 17.07.2009, 1 ♂ (A. Drozdovska, Yu. Verves). Zhy-

tomyr Region: Luka-Barska, 49°09'09"N, 27°47'54"E village, 14.07.1988, 1 ♂ (S. Zhrazhevsky).

Remarks. Larvae were found in nests of sphecoid wasp *Sceliphron caementarium* in Romagna, Italy (Campadelli et al., 1999). In Poland flying period is continued from March to October; flies were collected at flowers of *Euphorbia cyparissias* (Draber-Moňko, 2004). In Ukraine flies were collected from the beginning of March to the end of August at meadows, sandy areas, in cultural landscapes (Verves, 2005c).

Pollenia hungarica Rognes, 1987

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe: Austria, Belarus, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Norway, Poland, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtzi, Kher-son, Kyiv, Odesa, Poltava*, Sumy, Volyn, Zakarpattya, Zaporizhzhya and Zhytomyr* regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Trakhtemyriv village, 49°57'20"N, 31°22'39"E, bushes, 13.07.1988, 1 ♂; *ibid.*, bank of stream, 12.07.1988, 1 ♀ (S. Zhrazhevsky). Kyiv City: Berizka Lake, 50°26'17"N, 30°34'41"E 22.06. — 20.09.2006, 1 ♂, 3 ♀ (Yu. Verves); Druzhby Narodiv Park, 50°30'16"N, 30°32'31"E, meadows nr Lake, 30.07.2008, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves & K. Szpila); Dubky Lake, 50°28'32"N, 30°25'43"E, 15.07.2005, 35 ♂, 1 ♀; *ibid.*, 27.09.2006, 1 ♀; Golosieve Park in memory Maxim Ryl-sky, 50°23'22"N, 30°30'00"E, 10.06.2009, 12 ♂, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves); Golosievsky Lakes, 50°22'30"N, 30°30'30"E, humid meadows, 21.09.2003, 1 ♀ (A. Drozdovska); Kozacha street, 50°24'01"N, 30°30'05"E; on leaves & walls, 7.07.2005, 2 ♂; Kyiv-Pechersk Lavra, 50°26'06"N, 30°33'26"E, bushes at hills, 21.05.2009, 1 ♂; Lisove Lake, 50°27'53"N, 30°40'34"E, 20.07.2004, 1 ♂, 2 ♀; Lysa Gora hills, 50°23'42"N, 30°32'54"E, bushes, 19.08.2004, 1 ♀; Malynivka Lake, 50°29'11"N, 30°34'18"E, 23.06.2005, 1 ♂; Sonyachne Lake, 50°38'22"N, 30°38'23"E 4.10.2006, 1 ♂; Sovky Ponds, 50°24'35"N, 30°30'00"E, humid meadow, 3.05.2004, 1 ♂; *ibid.*, 11.07.2005, 2 ♂, 2 ♀; Verbne Lake, 50°29'24"N, 30°31'11"E 21.04.2004, 3 ♂, 1 ♀; Vasylykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 23.06. — 8.08.2008, 25 ♂; 23.06. — 28.07.2009, 2 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv Region: Bila Tserkva, Park Oleksandriya, 49°48'47"N, 30°04'09"E, 3.05.2009, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves); Irpin, 50°31'11"N, 30°14'40"E, 1–15.07.1997, 1 ♂ (V. Gorobchyshyn); Irpin River, 50°31'05"N, 30°15'33"E, forest nr bog, 19.04.2003, 3 ♂ (Yu. Verves); Novosilky village, 50°37'25"N, 30°38'36"E, forest board, 23.06. & 4.07.1984, 3 ♀ (A. Kotenko); Oseschyna village, 50°34'33"N, 30°32'26"E, coast of lake, meadows, 3.06.2007, 3 ♂, 1 ♀; Stugna River, 50°09'23"N, 30°44'01"E, 21.08.2004, at leaves and ground at border of pine forest near lake, 1 ♂; Tulyntsi village, 49°49'18"N, 31°10'49"E, feather-grass steppe with bushes, 4.06.2003, 1 ♂; (Yu. Verves). Poltava Region: Hrabarivka village, 50°22'52"N, 32°20'39"E, meadows near Ruda River, 15.07.2009, 2 ♂; Keybalivka village, 50°18'34"N, 32°30'10"E, meadows near Uday River, 14–18.07.2009, 5 ♂; Leliaky village, 50°19'41"N, 32°29'34"E, 19 & 21.07.2005, 2 ♂ (A. Drozdovska, Yu. Verves). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, at wooden fences, 8–11.05.2009, 2 ♂; *ibid.*, banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 4 males, 3 ♀ (Yu. Verves), Shevchenkove village, 50°31'19"N, 33°59'07"E, 25.07.1989, 1 ♀ (S. Zhrazhevskiy). Zakarpattya Region: Kolochava village, 48°26'12"N, 23°44'00"E, meadows, 17.08.1995, 10 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Zhytomyr Region: Polissya Nature Reserve, 44°54'N, 35°11'E, 13–17.07.2007, 6 ♂, 4 ♀ (O. Moroz).

Remarks. Larvae develop in living earthworms *Eisenia rosea* (Oligochaeta: Lumbricidae). Imagoes fly in March–October, with a peak in March; occasional specimens captured in November and February; in Central Europe found at altitudes to 1600 m a. s. l. (Rognes, 1987b, 1991). In Ukraine flies were collected from the beginning of March

to the end of October with peaks in March and June–July at different meadows and sandy areas, in bushes, forests, and in synanthropic habitats; for wintering imago concentrated into buildings (Verves, 2005c).

Pollenia labialis Robineau-Desvoidy, 1863

Distribution. Holarctic: Europe, including British Is.; Asia: Georgia; Africa: Algeria. North America: Canada (Ontario); USA (Indiana, Michigan, Maine, New Hampshire, Oregon, Washington). Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtzi, Kyiv, Mykolaiv*, Poltava*, Sumy*, Volyn and Zakarpattya regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Denhy village, 49°36'13"N, 32°10'36"E, 14.04.1989, 1 ♀ (S. Zhrazhevsky); Uman, Park Sophiivka, 48°44'29"N, 30°13'43"E, 13–14.06.2006, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv City: Lopukhovate I., 50°30'22"N, 30°33'20"E, 26.09.2008, 2 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv Region: Oseschyna village, 50°34'33"N, 30°32'26"E, coast of lake, meadows, 3.06.2007, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Poltava Region: Pyryatyn, 50°15'N, 32°32'E district, Hrabarivka village, 50°22'52"N, 32°20'39"E, meadows nr Ruda River, 15.07.2009, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Mykolaiv Region: debris of antic Olvia, 46°41'18"N, 31°53'14"E, 16.07.2006, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 2 ♂ (Yu. Verves); Romenka River, 50°47'42"N, 33°26'01"E, meadows, 25.07.1989, 1 ♂ (S. Zhrazhevskiy);

Remarks. Adults fly in March–November (Rognes, 1987a, 1991); flies were collected in Ukraine from the end of June to the middle of October with a peak in August at different meadows and sandy areas; relatively rare in cultural localities (Verves, 2005c).

Pollenia pediculata Macquart, 1834

Distribution. Holarctic: Europe: Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy (incl. Sardinia and Sicilia), Macedonia, Montenegro, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Serbia-Montenegro, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, The Netherlands, Ukraine, United Kingdom; Asia: China (Qinghai, Xinjiang), Cyprus, Gaza Strip, Iran, Israel, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Lebanon, Madeira, [North] Yemen, Syria, Tibet, Turkey, Turkmenistan; Africa: Egypt; North America: Canada (Alberta, British Columbia, Manitoba, New Britain, New Scotia, Newfoundland, Ontario, P. E. I., Quebec), USA (California, Colorado, District Columbia, Idaho, Illinois, Indiana, Iowa, Maine, Maryland, Massachusetts, North Carolina, New Hampshire, New Mexico, New York, North Carolina, Ohio, Oregon, Pennsylvania, Utah, Virginia, Washington, Wisconsin); Oriental Region: India (Jammu & Kashmir), Pakistan (Baluchistan, North-West Frontier Province, Northern Areas); Australasian/Oceanian Region: New Zealand. Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Crimea, Dnipropetrovsk, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kherison, Kyiv, Lviv*, Lugansk*, Mykolaiv, Odesa*, Poltava*, Sumy*, Vinnytzya, Zaporizhzhya and Zhytomyr regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Uman, Park Sophiivka, 48°44'29"N, 30°13'43"E, 11.06.2005, 4 ♀; *ibid.*, 13–14.06.2006, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Crimea: Beregove village, 44°54'20"N 33°37'E, sandy area,

10.08.2004, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv City: Baykove Cementery, 50°25'02"N, 30°30'37"E, 16.08.2004, 1 ♂, 2 ♀; Druzhby Narodiv Park, 50°30'16"N, 30°32'31"E, meadows nr Lake, 8.07.2005, 2 ♂, 2 ♀; Dubky Lake, 50°28'32"N, 30°25'43"E, 28.06. & 15.07.2005, 2 ♂; *ibid.*, 27.09.2006, 2 ♂; Golosieve Park in memory Maxim Rylsky, 50°23'22"N, 30°30'00"E, 10.06.2009, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves); Golosievsky Lakes, 50°22'30"N, 30°30'30"E, humid meadows, 21.09.2003, 1 ♂ (A. Drozdovska); Lopukhovate I., 50°30'22"N, 30°33'20"E, 26.09.2008, 5 ♂, 12 ♀; Lysa Gora hills, 50°23'42"N, 30°32'54"E, bushes, 19.08.2004, 2 ♂, 2 ♀; Malynivka Lake, 50°29'11"N, 30°34'18"E, 23.06.2005, 4 ♂, 2 ♀; Sovky Ponds, 50°24'35"N, 30°30'00"E, humid meadow, 27.08.2004, 1 ♀; Unnamed Dniipro Island, 50°30'22"N, 30°38'23"E, 16. — 30.05.2008, 2 ♂, 2 ♀; Vasylykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 23.06. — 18.07.2008, 4 ♂, 2 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv Region: Tulyntsi village, 49°49'18"N, 31°10'49"E, feather-grass steppe with bushes, 4.06.2003, 3 ♂, 1 ♀; 5.07.2007, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Lviv Region: Unnamed channel, 50°27'41"N, 24°17'30"E, steppe meadow, 18.07.1989, 1 ♀ (S. Zhrazhevsky). Lugansk Region: Kondrashivska Station, 48°39'18"N, 39°28'30"E, sandy area, 1.08.2008, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Drozdovska). Mykolaiv Region: Parutyne village, 46°42'24"N, 31°53'48"E, bank of sea, 15.07.2006, 4 ♂; debris of antic Olvia, 46°41'18"N, 31°53'14"E, 16.07.2006, 3 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Odesa Region: Kyslytsia village, 45°24'53"N, 29°02'41"E, 7. & 9.08.2009, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (V. Gorobchshyn). Poltava Region: Hrabarivka village, 50°22'52"N, 32°20'39"E, meadows nr Ruda River, 15.07.2009, 10 ♂, 5 ♀; Hurbyntsi village, 50°21'36"N, 32°28'35"E, on flowering Apiaceae, 18.07.2005, 20 ♂, 2 ♀; Keybalivka village 50°18'34"N, 32°30'10"E, meadows near Uday River, 15. & 18.07.2009, 3 ♂; Leliaky village, 50°19'41"N, 32°29'34"E, 19 & 21.07.2005, 3 males, 3 females; Ulyanivka village, meadows, 13.07.09, 1 ♂; Velyki Solontsi locality, 50°14'51"N, 32°35'10"E, 13–14.07.2009, 5 ♂ (A. Drozdovska, V. Gorobchshyn, Yu. Protzenko, Yu. Verves). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 7 ♂, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves); Vakalivshchyna village, 51°01'47"N, 34°55'12"E, humid meadow, 18–31.05.2006, 2 ♂ (O. Govorun). Zaporizhzhya Region: environs of Altagir village, 46°37'33.24"N, 35°16'57.36"E, Biological station of Melitopol National Pedagogical University, meadows & bushes, 4–15.06.2008, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Zhytomyr Region: Polissya Nature Reserve, 44°54'N, 35°11'E, 13–17.07.2007, 6 ♂, 13 ♀ (O. Moroz).

Remarks. Larvae are developed in earthworms *Eisenia rosea* (Oligochaeta: Lumbricidae). Larvae attacked earthworms *Allolobophora chlorotica* and *Aporrectodea caliginosa*, but earthworms easily destroyed the fly larvae by producing high amounts of slime (Szpila, 2003). Females attract to fish bate; flying period continues from February to October, several specimens have been captured during winter; in N America, Central and Northern Europe peak in early spring; flies collected at altitudes to 2500 m a. s. l. (Rognes, 1987b, 1991; Yahnke, George, 1972). In Ukraine flies were collected from the beginning of March to the end of October with peaks in March and August. Imagoes enter to buildings for wintering in autumn and feed on flowers *Prunus spinosa*, *Solidago canadensis*, *Thymus* sp. This polytopic species is very common in different natural and cultural localities (Verves, 2005c).

Pollenia rudis (Fabricius, 1794)

Distribution. Holarctic: Europe, including British Is.; Asia: Afghanistan, Armenia, Azerbaijan, China (Qinghai), Crete, Gaza Strip, Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Japan, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Kyrgyzstan, Lebanon, Mongolia, Russia (Siberia, Far East), Saudi Arabia, Syria, Tajikistan, Tibet, Turkey, Turkmenistan. Uzbekistan, West Bank; North Africa: Algeria, Azores, Canary Is., Egypt, Morocco,

Tunisia; North America: Canada (P. E. I., Quebec), USA (California, Idaho, Illinois, Indiana, Iowa, Kentucky, Massachusetts, New York, North Carolina, Oregon). Oriental Region: India (Jammu & Kashmir), Nepal, Pakistan (Baluchistan, North-West Frontier Province, Northern Areas). Australasian/Oceanian Region: Hawaii; New Zealand. Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtzi, Dnipropetrovsk, Kyiv, Lugansk*, Mykolaiv*, Poltava*, Sumy, Volyn, Zakarpattya, Zaporizhzhya* and Zhytomyr regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Kaniv Nature Reserve, 49°43'04"N, 31°29'52"E, yard, at vegetation, 10.06.2006, 1 ♂ (A. Drozdovska); Krugly I., 49°43'39"N, 31°34'36"E, 30.07.1989, 1 ♀; Trakhtemyriv village, 49°57'20"N, 31°22'39"E, bank of stream, 12.07.1988, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves); Tubiltsi village, 49°34'12"N, 31°40'48"E, 4.09.1988, 3 ♀ (S. Zhrazhevsky); Uman, Park Sophivka, 48°44'29"N, 30°13'43"E, 11.06.2005, 1 ♂; *ibid.*, 13–14.06.2006, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv City: Baykove Cementery, 50°25'02"N, 30°30'37"E, 16.08.2004, 2 ♀; Berizka Lake, 50°26'17"N, 30°34'41"E, 20.09.2006, 6 ♂, 4 ♀; Chervonozoryany Prospekt, 50°24'23"N, 30°30'34"E, Eat trunks of trees, 27.09.2006, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; Druzhby Narodiv Park, 50°30'16"N, 30°32'31"E, meadows nr lake, 8.07.2005, 10 ♂, 1 ♀; *ibid.*, 30.07.2008, 1 ♂, 2 ♀; Dubky Lake, 50°28'32"N, 30°25'43"E, humid meadow nr pond, 15.07.2005, 13 ♂, 2 ♀; *ibid.*, 27.09.2006, 2 ♂, 5 ♀; Golosieve Park in memory Maxim Rylsky, 50°23'22"N, 30°30'00"E, 10.06.2009, 44 ♂; Golosievsky Lakes, 50°22'30"N, 30°30'30"E, humid meadows, 21.09.2003, 2 ♂; Kozacha street, 50°24'01"N, 30°30'05"E, on leaves & walls, 7.07.2005, 1 ♂; Lopukhovate I., 50°30'22"N, 30°33'20"E, 26.09.2008, 3 ♀; Verbne Lake, 50°29'24"N, 30°31'11"E, 21.04.2004, 2 ♂, 3 ♀; Sovky Ponds, 50°24'35"N, 30°30'00"E, humid meadow, 3.05. & 27.08.2004, 2 ♂, 5 ♀; *ibid.*, 11.07.2005, 1 ♂, 3 ♀; Vasylykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 23.06. — 8.08.2008, 35 ♂, 10 ♀; *ibid.*, 15. — 23.06.2009, 3 ♂ (Yu. Verves); Uralaska street, 50°23'37"N, 30°31'30"E, 3–6.07.2009, 1 ♀ (A. Drozdovska). Kyiv Region: Bila Tserkva, Park Oleksandriya, 49°48'47"N, 30°04'09"E, 3.05.2009, 4 ♀ (Yu. Verves); Irpin, 50°31'11"N, 30°14'40"E, 1–15.07.1997, 9 ♂ (V. Gorobchshyn); Irpin River, 50°31'05"N, 30°15'33"E, 19.04.2003, 4 ♂; Oseschyna village, 50°34'33"N, 30°32'26"E, coast of lake, meadows, 3.06.2007, 15 ♂; Stugna River, 50°09'23"N, 30°44'01"E, 4 km W, 21.08.2004, at leaves and ground at border of pine forest nr lake, 1 ♂; Tulyntsi village, 49°49'18"N, 31°10'49"E, feather-grass steppe with bushes, 4.06.2003, 1 ♀; (Yu. Verves). Lugansk Region: Kondrashivska Station, 48°39'18"N, 39°28'30"E, sandy area, 1.08.2008, 1 ♂ (A. Drozdovska). Mykolaiv Region: Parutyne village, 46°42'24"N, 31°53'48"E, bank of sea, 16.07.2006, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Poltava Region: Hrabarivka village, 50°22'52"N, 32°20'39"E, meadows nr Ruda River, 15.07.2009, 3 ♂, 1 ♀; Hurbyntsi village, 50°21'36"N, 32°28'35"E, on flowering *Apiaceae*, 18.07.2005, 1 ♂; Keybalivka village 50°18'34"N, 32°30'10"E, meadows, 14., 17. & 18.07.2009, 3 ♂, 1 ♀; Leliaky village, 50°19'41"N, 32°29'34"E, 21.7.2005, 1 ♂; Ulyanivka village, 50°07'51"N, 32°33'21"E, meadows, 13.07.09, 1 ♀; Velyki Solontsi locality, 50°14'51"N, 32°35'10"E, 13–14.07.2009, 7 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Drozdovska, V. Gorobchshyn, Yu. Protzenko, Yu. Verves). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 4 ♂, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Zakarpattya Region: Kolochava village, 48°26'12"N, 23°44'00"E, 17.08.1995, 6 ♂, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Zaporizhzhya Region: environs of Altagir village, 46°37'33.24"N, 35°16'57.36"E, Biological station of Melitopol National Pedagogical University, meadows & bushes, 23.08.1997, 1 ♂; *ibid.*, 4–15.06.2008, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Zhytomyr Region: Polissya Nature Reserve, 44°54'N, 35°11'E, 13–17.07.2007, 6 ♂, 4 ♀ (O. Moroz).

Remarks. Larvae are parasites of earth worms *Allolobophora chlorotica* (Richards & Morrison, 1973) and *Eisenia rosea* (Thomson & Davies, 1973; Yahnke & George, 1972); bred from lepidopteran larvae *Chondrostegia maghrebica* (Chrysalidae) (Rognes, 1987b) and *Phragmatobia fuliginosa* (Arctiidae) (Sannino et al., 1988) too. Adults are active during all months, but maximum occur-

ance in April and July (Rognes, 1991). Imago feed at excreta of different homopters and flowering plants (Draber-Moňko, 2004). In Ukraine flies were collected from the beginning of March to the end of October with peaks in March and June. Imago enter to buildings for wintering in autumn. This polytopic species is very common in different natural and cultural localities (Verves, 2005c).

Pollenia similis Jacentkovský, 1941

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe: Albania, Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Ukraine: Cherkasy, Kherson and Odesa* regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Uman, Park Sophiivka, 48°44'29"N, 30°13'43"E, 13–14.06.2006, 3 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Odesa Region: Kyslytsia village, 45°24'53"N, 29°02'41"E, 7. & 9.08.2009, 1 ♂ (V. Gorobchyshyn).

Remarks. In Central Europe flying period is continued from mid March to October (Čepelák, 1986); flies prefer *Festuco-Brometea*, *Rhamno-Prunetea*, *Arrhenatherion elatioris*, *Tilio-Carpinetum* and *Peusedano-Coryletum* plant communities (Szpila, 2000). In Ukraine flies were collected from May to June on ground field roads and sandy sea coast (Verves, 2005c).

Pollenia tenuiforceps Séguéy, 1928

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe: Bosnia & Herzegovina; Czech Republic, France, Hungary, Romania, Slovakia, Switzerland, Ukraine; North Africa: Algeria. Ukraine: Cherkasy, Kyiv and Poltava* regions.

Material examined. Kyiv Region: Irpin River, 50°31'05"N, 30°15'33"E, forest nr bog, 19.04.2003, 5 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Poltava Region: Leliaky village, 50°19'41"N, 32°29'34"E, 21.07.2005, 1 ♂ (A. Drozdovska).

Remarks. In Ukraine adults were found in meadows and anthropogenous habitats (Verves, 2005c).

Pollenia vagabunda (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution. Holarctic: Europe, including British Is.; Asia: Turkey; North Africa: Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia. North America: Canada (British Columbia, Nova Scotia, Prince Edward I.), USA (Maine, Massachusetts, New Hampshire, New York, Washington). Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernivtzi, Kirovograd*, Kyiv, Odesa, Zakarpattya and Zaporizhzhya regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Trakhtemyriv village, 49°57'20"N, 31°22'39"E, bank of stream, 12.07.1988, 1 ♂ (S. Zhrazhevsky). Kirovograd Region: Vasylivka, 48°50'20"N, 33°17'03"E, 18.06.1989, 2 ♂ (S. Zhrazhevsky). Kyiv City: Golosieve Park in memory Maxim Rylsky, 50°23'22"N, 30°30'00"E, 10.06.2009, 2 ♀; Sonyachne Lake, 50°38'22"N, 30°38'23"E, 10.10.2006, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves); Uralska street, 50°23'37"N, 30°31'30"E, 3–6.07.2009, 1 ♀ (A. Drozdovska).

Remarks. Pupae and adults were taken in a stem of *Zea mais* occupied by *Sesamia nomagrioides* (Lepidoptera) (Séguéy, 1941). Imago captured all through the year in Fennoscandia & Denmark; some specimens overwinter indoors (Rognes, 1991, 1992a). Adults were collected in

March-May and July-October with peaks in March-April and October at meadows, sandy areas, bushes and synanthropic localities; imago enter into buildings for wintering (Verves, 2005a).

Chrysomya albiceps (Wiedemann, 1819)

Distribution. Southern Palaearctic and Oriental Region: India (Punjab, Uttaranchal), Pakistan (Baluchistan, North-West Frontier Province, Northern Areas, Sind); throughout Afrotropical Region (including Aldabra Is., Cape Verde Is., Madagascar I., Mauritius I., Reunion I., Rodriguez I., St. Helena I., Seychelles Is., Socotra I.); Central and South America (Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Costa Rica, Ecuador, Guatemala, Mexico, Paraguay, Peru, Puerto Rico, Venezuela). Ukraine: Crimea, Kherson*, Kyiv, Odesa*, Sumy* and Zakarpattya regions.

Material examined. Kherson Region: Chornomorsky Nature Reserve, 46°20'N, 31°57'E, Solenoozerny branch, sandy area, 15–18.09.2007, 1 ♀ (O. Moroz). Kyiv City: Vasylykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 2.09.2009, 1 ♂; Verbne Lake, 50°29'24"N, 30°31'11"E, 31.08.2004, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Odesa Region: Izmail, 45°21'06"N, 28°50'11"E, 4–8.08.2009, 1 ♂ (V. Gorobchyshyn); Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, at wall of building, 22.08.2009, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Synanthropic species. Larvae develop in different dead vertebrate mammals, sometimes in dung; young larvae feed on the exudations of decomposing fresh, but 2nd & 3rd instar larvae should become predatory of another dipteran larvae (*Chrysomya megacephala*, *Cochliomyia macellaria*, *Muscina stabulans*, *Liopygia argyrostoma* etc.) and even cannibalistic. Larvae caused facultative cutaneous myiasis of humans and different mammals: camel, donkey, goat, livestock, and sheep. Flies feed on decomposed animal matters, fruits and flowering plants. This species has an valuable importance as a forensic indicator (Carvalho & Mello-Patiu, 2008; Faria et al., 2003; Fischer, 2007; Grassberger et al., 2003; Kurahashi & Kirk-Spriggs, 2006; Povolný, 2002; Rodrigues-Guimarães et al., 2004; Verves, 2004d). This species is known as vector of diseases: the helminth eggs found on their body surface and in intestinal content were identified as *Ascaris* sp., *Capillaria* sp., *Toxascaris* sp., *Toxocara* sp., *Trichuris* sp., Oxyuridae gen., sp., Trichostrongylidae gen., sp., and Acanthocephala. Besides eggs it was also found helminth larvae on the body surface of flies. There were significant differences between the sites related to the number of helminth eggs found on the flies (Oliveira et al., 2002). In Ukraine few specimens were collected in synanthropic habitats (Verves, 2005c).

Phormia regina (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution. Holarctic (absent in Scandanavia). Oriental: Pakistan (Sind) and Australasian/Oceanian (Hawaii) regions. Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtzi, Crimea, Kherson, Kyiv, Lugansk, Sumy* and Zakarpattya regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Uman, Park Sophiivka, 48°44'29"N, 30°13'43"E, 13–14.06.2006, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Kherson Region: Novooleksandrivka village, 46°19'44"N, 32°28'43"E, near pig farm,

at horse dung, 4.09.1961, 2 ♂, 1 ♀; near poultry farm, at horse and pig dung, 5.09.1961, 7 ♂, 2 ♀ (O. Viktorov-Nabokov). Kyiv City: Baykove Cemetery, 50°25'02"N, 30°30'37"E, 16.08.2004, 1 ♂; Dubky Lake, 50°28'32"N, 30°25'43"E, humid meadow, 15.07.2005, 7 ♂; Golosieve Park in memory Maxim Rylsky, 50°23'22"N, 30°30'00"E, 10.06.2009, 1 ♂; Kozacha street, 50°24'01"N, 30°30'05"E; on leaves & walls, 7.07.2005, 2 ♂; Verbne Lake, 50°29'24"N, 30°31'11"E 31.08.2004, 1 ♂; Vasylykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 28.07.2009, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 2 ♂ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Synanthropic species. Larvae are developed in dead animals and, rarely, faeces; breeds in lavatories, garbage piles and carcasses: Grunin, 1972 (Грунин, 1972), Kurahashi, 1967, Stackelberg, 1959 (Штакельберг, 1979); produced primary and secondary cutaneous myiasis of infants and adult humans (Adair, 1999; Alexis, Mittleman, 1988; Ali-Khan, Ali-Khan, 1975; Gaponov, 1995; Khan, Khan, 1985a, b; Miller et al., 1990; Reames et al., 1988) and sheep (Damsky et al., 1976; Hall, 1997; Hall, Wall, 1995; Otranto, Stewens, 2002; Seaquist et al., 1983). Imagoes are known as vector of poliomyelitis and other infectious diseases of the digestive organs (Greenberg, 1971, 1973); common near human dwellings at decaying animal and plant matters: Artamonov, 1997 (Артамонов, 1997) and Park, 1977. The maggots are universally available and very cost effective in larval therapy (Hall, Smith, 1993; Horn et al., 1976; Leclercq, 1990; Robinson, 1933; Sherman, Pechter, 1988). The period of flying activity continued from April to September in Slovakia (Čepelák, 1986) and in June–August in Poland (Draber-Moňko, 2004). In Ukraine adults were collected from the end of March to the beginning of October at meadows, swamps, sea coast, near human dwellings (Verves, 2005c).

Protocalliphora azurea (Fallén, 1817)

Distribution. All parts of Palaearctic Region; Oriental Region: China (Guizhou, Yunnan, Zhejiang) and Pakistan (North-West Frontier Province, Northern Areas). Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtzi, Dnipropetrovsk, Kherson, Kyiv, Lugansk, Poltava*, Volyn and Zaporizhzhya regions.

Material examined. Kyiv City: Dubky Lake, 50°28'32"N, 30°25'43"E, 15.07.2005, 2 ♀; Kozacha street, 50°24'01"N, 30°30'05"E; on leaves & walls, 7.07.2005, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv Region: Stugna River, 50°09'23"N, 30°44'01"E, 21.08.2004, at leaves and ground at border of pine forest near lake, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Poltava Region: Velyki Solontsi locality, 50°14'51"N, 32°35'10"E, 13.07.09, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Zaporizhzhya Region: Berdyansk spit, 46°41'10"N, 36°48'38"E, 14–17.08.1994, 2 ♂ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Larvae are bloodsucking at nestlings in nests of different birds' species after Bauchau, 1998; Cais et al., 2001; Draber-Moňko, 1997, 2002, 2004; Fan et al., 1997; Gaponov, 1997 (Гапонов, 1997); González-Mora & Peris, 1988; Hicks, 1959, 1962, 1971; Hori, Iwasa, 1988; Hurtrez-Bousses et al., 1999, 2000; Iwasa et al., 1995; Kerimov et al., 1985 (Керимов и др., 1985); Kovalev, Verves, 1987 (Ковалев, Вервес, 1987); Kurahashi, 1993; Merino, Potti, 1998; Moreno et al., 2002; Peus, 1960; Pinowski et al., 1997; Rognes, 1991, 2002; Shutova, 1986, 1997 (Шутова, 1986, 1987); Skufyin, Khitsova, 1978 (Скуфьин, Хицова,

1978); Tryjanowski et al., 2001. The list of hosts is such: Passeriformes: Alaudidae: *Alauda arvensis*; Certhidae: *Certhia familiaris*; Cinclidae: *Cinclus cinclus*; Corvidae: *Corvus corone cornix*, *C. corone corone*, *C. frugilegus*; Emberizidae: *Emberiza citrinella*, *Miliaria calandra*; Fringillidae: *Fringilla coelebs*, *Serinus canarius*; Hirundinidae — *Delichon urbica*, *Hirundo rustica*, *Riparia riparia*; Laniidae: *Lanius collurio*; Motacillidae: *Anthus pratensis*, *A. spinoletta*, *Motacilla alba*, *M. cinerea*; Muscicapidae: *Cyanoptila cyanomelana*, *Ficedula albicollis*, *F. hypoleuca*, *Muscicapa striata*, *Xanthopygia narcissina*; Paridae: *Parus ater*, *P. caeruleus*, *P. cinctus*, *P. cristatus*, *P. major*, *P. montanus*, *P. palustris hensoni*, *P. palustris palustris*, *P. rutilans*, *P. varius*; Ploceidae: *Passer domesticus*, *P. montanus*, *Petronia petronia*; Sittidae: *Sitta europaea*; Sturnidae: *Sturnus philippensis*, *S. vulgaris*; Sylviidae: *Phylloscopus collybita*, *P. sibilatrix*, *P. trochilus*, *Sylvia atricapilla*, *S. borin*, *S. cantillans*, *S. communis*; Troglodytidae: *Troglodytes troglodytes*; Turdidae: *Callocalis brevirostris innotuita*, *Erithacus rubecula*, *Luscinia* sp., *Oenanthe oenanthe*, *Phoenicurus ochruros*, *P. phoenicurus*, *Turdus chrysolaus*, *T. iliacus*, *T. merula*, *T. philomelos*; Piciformes: Picidae: *Junco torquilla*. Adults have been collected in Fennoscandia and Poland from April to September; feed on different flowering plants (Draber-Moňko, 2004; Rognes, 1991). In Ukraine adult specimens were collected in April–August in different natural (meadows, forests) and cultural (parks, gardens, etc) habitats (Verves, 2005c).

Protocalliphora falcozi Séguéy, 1928

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe: Austria, Czech Republic (Moravia), France (continental & Corsica); Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Romania, Russia (Tatars-tan), Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine; Asia: West Siberia (Novosibirsk Region). Ukraine: without detailed data after Grunin (Грунин, 1970b), Kyiv City*.

Material examined. Kyiv City: Vasylykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 8.08.2008, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Larvae are bloodsuckers of nestlings of birds *Ficedula albicollis*, *Muscicapa albicollis*, *Parus caerulescens*, *P. caeruleus*, *P. major*, *P. montanus*, *P. palustris*, *P. querulous*, *Phoenicurus phoenicurus*, *P. ochruros*, *Sturnus vulgaris*, after Borisova, 1983 (Борисова, 1983); Cais et al., 2001; González-Mora, Peris, 1988; Gregor, Povolný, 1959; Grunin, 1966 (Грунин, 1966); Hurtrez-Bousses et al., 1999; Lehrer, 1972; Peus, 1960; Rognes, 1997, 2003; Verves, 2005c). Larvae occur regularly in nests of *Parus major* and *P. caerulescens*, and is sometimes found in nests of other hole nesters (Wesołowski, 2001); in Central Europe flying period is continued from May to September (Čepelák, 1986). Flies feed at aphid's excrements (Borisova, 1983) and flowers of Apiaceae at xerothermic meadows (Draber-Moňko, 2004).

***Protocalliphora rognesi* Thompson & Pont, 1993**

Distribution. Widely distributed in Holarctics. Ukraine: Cherkasy, Crimea*, Dnipropetrovsk, Kyiv, Lugansk and Volyn regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Kaniv Nature Reserve, 49°43'04"N, 31°29'52"E, yard, 27.04.1959, 4 ♂; 5.05.1959, 1 ♂; on dead fish, 17.05.1959, 1 ♀; indoor of pigsty, 10.07.1959, 1 ♂ (O. Viktorov-Nabokov). Crimea: Kazantip Nature Reserve, 45°28'N, 35°50'E, on flowering *Apiaceae*, 26.07.2007, 1 ♂. Kyiv City: shores of Lakes nr Shevchenko Square, 27.09.2006, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Larvae are obligatory bloodsuckers of bank swallow, or sand martin (*Riparia riparia*) nestlings (Brothers, 1999; Cais et al., 2001; Nuorteva, 1960; Peus, 1960; Sabrosky et al., 1989; Whitworth, 2006). Flying period in June–August (Rognes, 1991); flies feed on flowers of different plants (Draber-Mońko, 2004). In Ukraine flies were collected at meadows in July–August (Verves, 2005c).

***Protophormia terraenovae* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)**

Distribution. Widespread in Holarctics, including such Arctic territories, as Faroes, Greenland, Iceland, Novaya Zemlya, Spitzbergen, Svalbard, Vaigach I., Wrangel I.; Oriental Region (Pakistan). The sites where this species was recorded in the Southern Hemisphere cover a range nearly extended between 54...51° S, and 36...72° W (Mariluis, Schnack, 2004): Neotropic: Argentina: East Falkland Is., Santa Cruz, Tierra del Fuego (Mariluis, Mulieri, 2003, Mariluis, Schnack, 2002, 2004;), Chile: Magellanes (Mariluis, 1999b). Antarctic: South Georgia Is. (Haenel et al., 1998). Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtzi, Crimea, Donetzk, Kharkiv, Kherson, Khmelnyzky, Kyiv, Lviv, Odesa, Poltava, Sumy*, Vinnytya, Volyn, Zakarpattia, Zaporizhzhya and Zhytomyr regions.

Material examined. Kyiv City: Baykove Cementery, 50°25'02"N, 30°30'37"E, 16.08.2004, 1 ♂; Dubky Lake, 50°28'32"N, 30°25'43"E, 15.07.2005, 1 ♂; Kozacha street, 50°24'01"N, 30°30'05"E, on leaves & walls, 7.07.2005, 4 ♂; Malynivka Lake, 50°29'11"N, 30°34'18"E, 23.06.2005, 4 ♂, 1 ♀; Vasykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 5.10.2009, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv Region: Irpin, 50°31'11"N, 30°14'40"E, 1–15.07.1997, 3 ♂, 1 ♀ (V. Gorobchynshyn); Irpin River, 50°31'05"N, 30°15'33"E, forest nr bog, 19.04.2003, 3 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Poltava Region: Keybalivka village 50°18'34"N, 32°30'10"E, meadows, 18.07.2009, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 2 ♂ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Synanthropic species. Larvae necrophagous (Davies, 1999; Nuorteva, 1971; Pulliainen, 1974); produced secondary cutaneous myiasis of humans (Adair, 1999; Zumpt, 1965), sheep (González-Mora, Peris, 1988; Hall, 1997; MacLeod, 1943a, b; Norris & Titcher, 1997; Otranto, Stewens, 2002), cattle (Hall, Smith, 1993), reindeer (*Rangifer tarandus*) according to Hall, 1948 and Kolomyietz, Gomoynova, 1971 (Коломиєць, Гомоюнова, 1971). In Fennoscandia and Poland flying period is continued from March to October; adult flies feed on carcasses, feces, flowers: Draber-Mońko, 2004; Rognes, 1991; Stackelberg, 1962 (Штакельберг, 1962). This species has importance as forensic indicator (Nuorteva, 1987). Maggots are universally available and very cost effective in larval therapy (Bunkis et al., 1985; Sherman, Pechter, 1988). The petrified puparia of this species were found in a skull of fossil mammals: *Coleodonta*

antiquitatis (Gauthier, 1975), mamutus (Heinrich, 1982; Gernonpre, Leclercq, 1993), bison (Gauthier, Schumann, 1973). The mass occurrence annoyed people living in rural houses over a radius of about 4 km around the storage area. Imagoes transmit different bacteria from intestinal group — *Citrogaster*, *Klebsiella*, *Proteus*, *Salmonella*: see González-Mora, Peris, 1988 and Mokrova et al., 1999 (Мокрова и др., 1999). In Ukraine flies were collected from May to September in different synanthropic and cultural localities (Verves, 2005c).

***Eurychaeta muscaria* (Meigen, 1824)**

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe: Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, France, Hungary, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Ukraine; Africa: Algeria, Tunisia. Ukraine: Chernivtzi and Ternopil regions.

Material examined. Ternopil Region: Zalischyky, 48°39'01"N, 25°44'00"E, coast of Dnister, 20–21.05.1986, 1 ♂ (S. Zhrazhevsky).

Remarks. Females macrolarviparous: give birth to a single very large (7 mm) 1st stage larva at about 2 weeks interval during the summer. It is deposited on dead pulmonate snails from family Helicidae: *Arianta arbustorum*, *Cepaea hortensis*, *Helix pomatia*, *Theba pisana* (Schmitz, 1910, 1917). Flying period in Poland is continued from May to August, flies are distributed in forests and mountains, adults feed at flowers of different plants (Draber-Movko, 2004).

***Eurychaeta palpalis* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)**

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Norway, Poland, Rumania, Russia: (Moscow, Leningrad and Voronezh regions), Serbia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, The Netherlands, Ukraine, United Kingdom (England only); Asia: Armenia, Russia (West Siberia). Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtzi, Crimea, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kharkiv, Kyiv, Poltava, Sumy, Vinnytsya, Volyn, Zakarpattia & Zhytomyr regions.

Material examined. Kyiv City: Feofania, 50°20'27"N, 30°29'20"E, mesophitic forest nr pond, 22.05.2008, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv Region: Tulyntsi village, 49°49'18"N, 31°10'49"E, feather-grass steppe with bushes, 29.05., 4.06.2003 & 15.06.2004, 3 ♀ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Macrolarviparous species (see above); larvae are developed in dead terrestrial snails *Arianta arbustorum*, *Cepaea hortensis*, *C. nemoralis*, *Helix pomatia*, *Theba pisana*. Adults had been collected from May to August, with maximum members in July or August (Draber-Mońko, 2004; Lundbeck, 1927; Rognes, 1986, 1991). In Ukraine flying period is continued from May to September with a peak in the end of May — beginning of June. Flies prefer humid meadows and bushes, sometimes in humid parks (Verves, 2005c).

***Rhyncomya peusi* (Zumpt, 1956)**

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe: Albania, Greece, Rumania, Ukraine; Asia: Crete, Cyprus, Israel, Lebanon, Oman, Saudi Arabia, Syria, Turkey. Ukraine: Kherson Region.

Material examined. Kherson Region: Chornomorsky Nature Reserve, 46°20'N, 31°57'E, Rybalchasnsky branch, on wooden wall of destroyed building, 22–24.07.2006, 56 ♂; ibid., Solenoozerny branch, on wooden wall of destroyed building, 28.07.2006, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). All specimens were collected between 16...19 hours.

Remarks. In Israel flying period is continued from April to September (Rognes, 2002). In Ukraine flies were collected on dry meadow, at flowers of *Euphorbia* sp. (Verves, 2005c).

***Rhyncomya speciosa* (Loew, 1844)**

Distribution. Europe: Albania, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Greece, Macedonia, Romania, Ukraine; Asia: Azerbaijan, Cyprus, Iran, Israel, Saudi Arabia, Syria, Turkey. Ukraine: Kharkiv, Kherson and Mykolaiv regions.

Material examined. Kherson Region: Chornomorsky Nature Reserve, 46°20'N, 31°57'E, Solenoozerny branch, sandy area, 20.07.2006, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves); 15–18.07.2007, 1 ♀ (O. Moroz). Mykolaiv Region: Kinburn sandy area, 46°26'04"N, 31°42'15"E, 10.05.2004, 1 ♀ (Yu. Protzenko).

Remarks. In Israel flying period is continued from June to September, with peak in August (Rognes, 2002). In Ukraine flies were collected on dry meadow, at flowers of *Euphorbia* sp. (Verves, 2005c).

***Stomorhina lunata* (Fabricius, 1805)**

Distribution. Palaearctic: Europe: Albania, Balearic Is., Belgium, Czech Republic (Moravia), France (continental part and Corsica), Finland, Germany, Hungary, Italy (continental part, Sardinia, Sicilia), Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia (Chechnya), Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, The Netherlands, Ukraine, United Kingdom; Asia: Armenia, Azerbaijan, China (Sichuan, Xizang), Cyprus, Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Kyrgyzstan, Lebanon, [North] Yemen, Saudi Arabia, Syria, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan; North Africa: Algeria, Canary Is., Egypt, Madeira I., Morocco, Spanish North Africa; Nearctic Region: Bermuda Is.; Oriental Region: China (Yunnan), India (Assam, Tamil Nadu, Uttaranchal, West Bengal), Malaysia (Malaya), Nepal, Pakistan (Baluchistan), Taiwan; widespread in Afrotropical and Madagascan regions. Ukraine: Cherkasy*, Crimea, Kyiv*, Odesa* and Poltava regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Uman, Park Sophiivka, 48°44'29"N, 30°13'43"E, 14.06.2006, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv Region: Tulyntsi village, 49°49'18"N, 31°10'49"E, feather-grass steppe with bushes, 10.07.2007, 1 ♂ (K. Szpila). Odesa Region: Suvorove village, 45°35'08"N, 28°59'00"E, 20–23.08.2009, 1 ♀ (V. Gorobchshyn).

Remarks. Larvae had been found in oothecae of acrids *Doclostaurus maroccanus*, *Schistocerca gregaria*, *S. peregrina* (Cuthbertson, 1934). They are probably not restricted to these insects, but have also been found in association with dead and dying termite workers and soldiers in the broken-

down fungus beds of a termite nest (Cuthbertson, 1935; Ferrar, 1987; Kurahashi, Kirk-Spriggs, 2006). Flies have been bred from beneath termite infested cow-dung too (Senior White et al., 1940). In Israel the imagoes are active during all year (Rognes, 2002). Adults feed at flowers of *Solidago* sp. (Szpila, 2000).

Rhinophoridae

In Ukraine, the occurrence of 15 species of rhinophorid flies has been recorded so far after Belanovskiy, 1951 (Белановский, 1951) and Verves, 2005, a-b). The Ukrainian fauna of those flies is poorly studied.

***Melanophora roralis* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Distribution. Holarctic: Europe, including British Is., up to Norway; North Africa: Azores, Algeria; North America: USA (Maryland; Kansas to Michigan and New Hampshire, south to Louisiana & Florida; North Carolina). Afrotropical: Cape Verde Is. Neotropic: Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Jamaica, St. Thomas I. Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Crimea, Kyiv, Poltava, Zaporizhzhya* and Zhytomyr* regions.

Material examined. Kyiv City: Baykove Cemetery, 50°25'02"N, 30°30'37"E, 16.08.2004, 2 ♂; Kozacha street, 50°24'01"N, 30°30'05"E, at walls of buildings, 22.06. — 4.10.2009, 15 ♂; Vasylykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 23.06. — 8.08.2008, 24 ♂, 1 ♀; ibid., 18.05. — 2.10.2009, 59 ♂, 5 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Zaporizhzhya Region: environs of Altgir village, 46°37'33.24"N, 35°16'57.36"E, Biological station of Melitopol National Pedagogical University, meadows & bushes, 4–15.06.2008, 31 ♂, 2 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Zhytomyr Region: Polissya Nature Reserve, 44°54'N, 35°11'E, 13–17.07.2007, 1 ♀ (O. Moroz).

Remarks. Larvae are the internal parasites of woodlice *Armadillum* sp., *Oniscus asellus*, *Porcellio scaber*, *P. spinicornis* (Bedding, 1973; Clemons, 2001, 2003; Guimarães, 1977; Thompson, 1934). Females place eggs mainly at higher altitudes of walls and occasionally trees, between 1 & 3 meters; males gathered in considerable numbers on sun exposed walls, tree trunks and gravestones; because of the very typical flight pattern the males could be identified easily from a distance; from beginning of May to the beginning of October (Wijnhoven, 2001). Adult flies feed on flowers of *Achillea millefolium* (Verves, 2005a, b).

***Phyto melanocephala* (Meigen, 1824)**

Distribution. Palaearctic: Southern and Middle Europe, including British Is. Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Chernivtzi, Crimea, Kyiv, Kherson*, Odesa*, Sumy* and Zaporizhzhya regions.

Material examined. Crimea: Kanaka gully, 44°48'N, 34°41'E, meadows, 5–8.05.2005, 1 ♂; Kazantip Nature Reserve, 45°28'N, 35°50'E, 10–13.05.2005, 1 ♂, 2 ♀ (L. Khrokalo & A. Kotenko). Kherson Region: Chornomorsky Nature Reserve, 46°20'N, 31°57'E, Solenoozerny branch, coast of sea, 29.07.2006, 3 ♂ (V. Gorobchshyn & Yu. Verves); Tsiurupynsk, 46°37'12"N, 32°43'12"E, 29.07.2008, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv City: Baykove Cemetery, 50°25'02"N, 30°30'37"E, 16.08.2004, 3 ♂; ibid., 20.06.2009, 1 ♂, 2 ♀; Olzhyn I., 50°16'50"N, 30°39'20"E, 25.06.2009, 1 ♂; Unnamed Dnipro Island, 50°30'22"N, 30°38'23"E, 29.08.2008, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Odesa Region: Izmail, 45°21'06"N, 28°50'11"E district, Suvorove village, 45°35'08"N, 28°59'00"E village,

20–23.08.2009, 8 ♂, 8 ♀ (V. Gorobchyshyn). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, at wooden fences, 8–11.05.2009, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Zaporizhzhya Region: environs of Altagir village, 46°37'33.24"N, 35°16'57.36"E, Biological station of Melitopol National Pedagogical University, meadows & bushes, 4–15.06.2008, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Larvae develop in living woodlice *Armadillidium nasatum*, *A. quinquestriatus*, *A. silvestri*, *A. versicolor*, *A. vulgare*, *Oniscus asellus*, *Porcellio scaber*, *P. spinicornis* (Bedding, 1973; Clemons, 2001; Thompson 1934). Flies were collected at meadows from the middle of May to the end of September, feeding at flowers of different plants after Belanovskiy 1951 (Белановский, 1951); Draber-Moňko 1989; Verves 2005a, b. The females place eggs mainly at soil surface level; males gathered in considerable numbers on sun exposed walls, tree trunks and gravestones; 3 generations per year (Wijnhoven, 2001).

Rhinomorinia sarcophagina (Schiner, 1862)

Palaeartic: Europe: Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Czech Republic, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Slovakia, Switzerland, Ukraine: Chernivtz, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Lugansk* and Poltava* regions.

Material examined. Kyiv Region: Stugna River, 50°09'23"N, 30°44'01"E, at leaves and ground at border of pine forest nr Lake, 21.08.2004, 1 ♂; Tulyntsi village, 49°49'18"N, 31°10'49"E, feather-grass steppe with bushes, 4.06.2003 & 12.05.2004, 4 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Lugansk Region: Diakove village, 47°56'58"N, 39°08'24"E, 9.07.2000, 1 ♀ (S. Konovalov). Poltava Region: Hrabarivka village, 50°22'52"N, 32°20'39"E, meadows nr Ruda River, 15.07.2009, 1 ♀; Shkuraty village, 50°12'41"N, 32°40'26"E, meadows, 17.07.2009, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves).

Rhinophora lepida (Meigen, 1824)

Distribution. Palaeartic: Europe: Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Russia (Leningrad and Voronyezh regions, Krasnodarskiy Krai, and Dagestan), Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, The Netherlands, United Kingdom (south England). Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernigiv, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kherson, Kyiv, Lugansk, Mykolaiv, Poltava*, Sumy*, Vinnytzya and Zaporizhzhya Regions.

Material examined. Cherkasy Region: Uman, Park Sophiivka, 48°44'29"N, 30°13'43"E, 13–14.06.2006, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Kyiv City: Olzhyn I., 50°16'50"N, 30°39'20"E, 16.09.2009, 1 ♀ (Yu. Verves). Poltava Region: Keybalivka village 50°18'34"N, 32°30'10"E, meadows nr Uday River, 17–18.07.2009, 2 ♀; Velyki Solontsi locality, 50°14'51"N, 32°35'10"E, 13–14.07.2009, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves). Sumy Region: Romny, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, 50°46'N, 33°27'E, banks of Romenka River, meadows and bushes, 21–27.08.2009, 33 ♂, 4 ♀ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Larvae are specialized parasites of woodlice *Porcellio scaber* (Bedding, 1973). The females lay eggs separately underneath stones, tree bark, pieces of cement and in crevices of walls; flying period from June to the middle of August. The males significantly appeared earlier than the females, the difference being about 10 days (Wijnhoven, 2001). Adult flies feed on flowers of different plants after Belanovskiy, 1951 (Белановский, 1951); Clemons, 2001; Verves, 2005b.

Stevenia nudiseta Belanovsky, 1951

Distribution. Palaeartic: Europe: Ukraine: Donetsk, Lugansk* and Odesa* regions.

Material examined. Lugansk Region: Kondrashivka Station, 48°39'18"N, 39°28'30"E, sandy area, 1.08.2008, 3 ♂ (A. Drozdovska). Odesa Region: Suvorove village, 45°35'08"N, 28°59'00"E, 20–23.08.2009, 1 ♂ (V. Gorobchyshyn).

Stevenia umbratica (Fallén, 1820)

Distribution. Palaeartic: Europe: Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic (Bohemia), France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, The Netherlands, Ukraine; North Africa: Algeria. Ukraine: Kyiv City and Odesa Region.

Material examined. Kyiv City: Vasylykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 5.07.2008, 1 ♀; 15.06.2009, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. The flying period is continued from beginning of May to the 3rd decade of September. Adult flies feed at flowers of *Heracleum sphondylium*; females lay eggs separately underneath stones, tree bark, pieces of cement and in crevices of walls (Wijnhoven, 2001).

Tricogena rubricosa (Meigen, 1824)

Distribution. Palaeartic: Europe: Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Russia (Leningrad Region), Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom. Ukraine: Kyiv and Zhytomyr regions.

Material examined. Kyiv City: Kozacha street, 50°24'01"N, 30°30'05"E, on leaves, 7.07.2005, 1 ♂; Vasylykivska street, 50°23'32"N, 30°29'21"E, 18.06. — 2.10.2009, 6 ♂, 2 ♀ (Yu. Verves).

Remarks. Larvae bred from woodlice *Oniscus asellus* and *Porcellio scaber* (Clemons, 2001; Thompson 1934). The females place eggs mainly at soil surface level; visit flowers; dead woodlouse *P. scaber* most fanatically scavenged by 7 females. The flying period is continued from the mid of April to the early September (Wijnhoven, 2001; Wijnhoven, Zeegers, 1999). Adult flies feed at flowers of *Achillea millefolium* (Ziegler, Lange, 2001) and *Solidago canadensis* (Verves, 2005a, b).

Discussion

Two species (*Bellardia vespillo* and *Lucilia cuprina*) are firstly recorded for Ukrainian fauna. As a result, the list of Ukrainian calliphorids increased to 69 species. 20 species of Calliphoridae are firstly recorded for Sumy, 19 for Poltava regions, 7 for Kyiv City, 6 for Odesa, 4 for Mykolayiv, 3 for Krym Republic (Crimea), Ivano-Frankivsk, Kherson, Zhytomyr, 2 for Kyiv, Lugansk, Lviv, a single species for Cherkasy, Kirovograd, Rivne, Ternopil, Volyn, Zakarpattia and Zaporizhzhya Regions. From 15 known species of Rhinophoridae two ones are firstly recorded for Lugansk, Odesa, Poltava, Sumy, a single species for Kherson, Zaporizhzhya, Zhytomyr regions. The data on species of regional faunas are given in the Table 1.

Table 1

Number of species of calliphorid and rhinophorid flies in Ukrainian regional faunas

Regions (in alphabetical order)	Number of species					
	Calliphoridae			Rhinophoridae		
	previously known	firstly recorded	total	previously known	firstly recorded	total
Cherkasy	43	1	44	5	-	5
Chernigiv	30	-	30	4	-	4
Chernivtsi	34	-	34	2	-	2
Crimea	20	3	23	4	-	4
Dnipropetrovsk	10	-	10	1	-	1
Donetz'k	7	-	7	4	-	4
Ivano-Frankivsk	6	3	9	2	-	2
Kharkiv	11	-	11	2	-	2
Kherson	17	3	20	1	1	2
Khmel'nytskyi	6	-	6	1	-	1
Kirovograd	4	1	5	1	-	1
Kyiv City	19	7	26	5	-	5
Kyiv Region	39	2	41	2	-	2
Lugansk	14	2	16	2	2	4
Lviv	7	2	9	1	-	1
Mykolayiv	4	4	8	1	-	1
Odesa	9	6	15	2	2	4
Poltava	9	19	28	1	2	3
Rivne	2	1	3	-	-	-
Sumy	7	20	27	-	2	2
Ternopil	3	1	4	1	-	1
Vinnitsya	8	-	8	2	-	2
Volyn	21	1	22	1	-	1
Zakarpattia	24	1	25	2	-	2
Zaporizhzhya	16	1	17	4	1	5
Zhytomyr	8	3	11	1	1	2
Ukraine in total	67	2	69	15	-	15

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